

Report

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Prepared by: Maria Lima-Toivanen, Freya M. Robinson, Mauro Amoruso, Santiago Cabaleiro, Ines Boujmil, Stela Karović, Leonardo Piccinetti, Aneesa Reeves, Fabio Bucollini

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MoM	Minutes of Meeting	
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WOR	Working document, issued as preparatory documents to a Technical report	
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List of Acronyms

ABT	AquaBio Tech, Malta
BAT	Best Available Technologies
Bugenvila	BUGENVILA INVESTICIJE DOO, Croatia
CFP	Common Fisheries Policy
CETGA	Centro Tecnológico del Cluster de la Acuicultura, Spain
CLL	Co-creation Living Labs
DEIMS-SDR	Dynamic Ecological Information Management System - Site and dataset registry information management system
EATIP	European Aquaculture Technology and Innovation Platform
eLTER	Integrated European Long-Term Ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological Research
EC	European Commission
EMFF	European Maritime and Fisheries Fund
EU	European Union
GLP	Good Laboratory Practice
GMP	Good Manufacturing Practice
HE	Horizon Europe
IPMA	Instituto Português do Mar e da Atmosfera, Portugal
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
LL	Living Lab
OXY	Oxyguard, Denmark
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
PESTLE	Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Legal and Environmental
PRIMA	Partnership on Research and Innovation in the Mediterranean Area
RAS	Recirculated Aquaculture Systems
RDI	Research, Development and Innovation
R&D	Research and Development
R&I	Research and Innovation
Sea2See	Innovative Blockchain Traceability Technology and Stakeholders' Engagement Strategy for Boosting Sustainable Seafood Visibility, Social Acceptance and Consumption in Europe
SBEP	Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats
VAT	Value Added Tax
WEFE	Water, Energy, Food Ecosystem

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Executive Summary

The goal of the FishEUTrust “*European Integration of New Technologies and Social-economic Solutions for Increasing Consumer Trust and Engagement in Seafood Products*” project is to defragment the current food system to ensure sustainability and deliver solutions for a transparent and traceable seafood supply chain necessary to promote high-end, pan-European farmed seafood. The innovation at the heart of FishEUTrust is integrating different actors into a digital platform that links technology providers, supply chain stakeholders, regulatory/policymakers and consumers.

As part of its mission, FishEUTrust will establish five Co-creation Living Labs (CLLs) in diverse environments: the Mediterranean Basin, the North Sea and the Atlantic Sea. These CLLs will enable user involvement in innovation and development processes and act as demonstrators for the consortium to test and validate digital and non-digital supply chain solutions. Examples include creating sustainable business models, exploiting Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) strategies for aquaculture, e.g., protecting cultural and culinary heritage, short food supply chains, exploiting underused fish species, and engaging in innovative activities to stimulate/nudge behavioral change. It will also develop tools for maximizing trust by guaranteeing the quality, safety, and traceability of seafood products based on intelligent control systems (sensors), a suite of tools integrating metagenomics, genetic biomarkers, isotopic techniques, and digital technologies (labelling, Product Passport/Blockchain). These tools will be integrated into a single cutting-edge digital FishEUTrust platform that will apply the latest in artificial intelligence, data science and human-computer interactions.

The innovation at the heart of FishEUTrust is the integration of different stakeholders, actors and consumer sectors in a common platform linking technology providers with supply chain stakeholders engaging directly with socioeconomic analysis informing optimized business models and regulatory/policy actors to co-develop tools, systems and protocols across the seafood value chain intended to increase consumer awareness, engagement, and confidence.

This deliverable (D1.2) reports on the implementation strategy for establishing the five CLLs. It also includes relevant task outputs (TO) as follows: TO1.1: Integrated LLs stakeholder map and analysis; TO1.2: Establishment of CLLs best practices and operational protocols; and TO1.3: Consolidation of the synergies with the existing network of LLs to implement an inclusive EU-level Web of LLs. The deliverable is also related to milestone MS1 the organization of the Contextual workshop in Malta.

TO1.1: Integrated LLs stakeholder map and analysis: Four hundred and thirty-five stakeholders were grouped under the quintuple helix categories, mainly representing the industry category and government organizations. The stakeholders were categorized based on their various roles in the value chain, with fish farmers and distributors being the most represented, closely followed by government bodies.

TO1.2: Establishment of CLLs best practices and operational protocols: established CLLs in partner countries covering three different areas, Mediterranean, Atlantic and North Sea, integrating across all sectors of the value chain to support the development, test and validation of the FishEUTrust deliverables: ABT (Malta) – traceability, CETGA (Spain) – fish health, OXY (Denmark) – data provision, Bugenvila (Croatia) – business to business (B2B) and IPMA (Portugal) – consumer. The task involved identifying the main elements affecting the aquaculture industry through a PESTLE analysis at the European and country levels to contextualize the operations of the CLLs. An integrated analysis of the results from the PESTLE and SWOT analyses of FishEUTrust CLLs highlighted the following commonalities:

- The CLLs act as a communication interface in all agents of the quintuple helix.
- The CLLs do not have any national or European funding for their financing.
- The CLLs have access to essential technologies to improve consumer confidence in the products of the fishery culture.
- Environmental regulations often become a wall that makes it impossible for aquaculture activity to continue to develop within the EU.

A protocol for the implementation of the CLLs was also prepared.

TO1.3: Consolidation of the synergies with the existing network of LLs to implement an inclusive EU-level Web of LLs: identified LLs and research infrastructures and other facilities dedicated to research and development and innovation in aquaculture and projects that are implementing LLs in fields related to aquaculture and the focus of FishEUTrust CLLs. Altogether, the project identified twenty-seven research centres and facilities which perform novel research, experimentation and support to innovation on demand by clients (government, companies, associations or other stakeholder types) and fifteen projects that are applying LLs as platforms for research, experimentation, and innovation involving real-world environments and users. These research and innovation infrastructures and LLs are then proposed to create a Europe-wide network of innovation co-creation platforms to build synergies with FishEUTrust CLLs.

The main recommendation arising from this study refers:

To promote understanding of the LL concept and leadership for the CLLs at the project and site level. This task involves fully implementing FishEUTrust CLLs, that are the heart of the project.

To value the LLs and innovation co-creation and support infrastructures mapped as learning and innovation collaboration sources. This value will be mobilized following a clear strategy to build synergies with the leadership's support.

To enhance effectiveness, there is potential in exploring the utilization of technical software for mapping relationships. However, this should only be pursued if specific project tasks demand such mapping.

To identify common elements in the operational context of CLLs across different sites. This assessment is essential and should inform a plan to address these elements within the project's activities, fostering peer learning and working towards the sustainability of CLLs.

To define what constitutes an environmental stakeholder. This clear definition will facilitate the proper categorization and identification of current and future stakeholders. FishEUTrust and the sister project SEA2SEE could collaborate on developing this definition, as it will be pertinent not only to the current Horizon Europe projects but also to future initiatives.

To apply more efficient approach for stakeholder mapping by integrating the stakeholder list development with the stakeholder engagement task. The missed opportunity to align the engagement strategy with the early stages of the mapping task necessitates a reconsideration. The stakeholder list, populated with information on potential engagement activities, could serve as a baseline for the stakeholder engagement task as the project progresses. This integration would enhance cohesion and maximize the impact of stakeholder involvement in the FishEUTrust project.

1 Introduction

Meeting the FOOD 2030 challenges in the context of global food scenarios, food demand will increase by approximately 60% by 2050 according to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO, 2020), which will require innovations/measures that will deliver sustainable, resilient, responsible, diverse, competitive, and inclusive food systems within the frame of a circular bioeconomy (blue economy) while providing a healthy diet and engaging EU communities. Seafood currently represents 17% of global animal protein production (Costello et al, 2021). According to FAO (2020), it corresponds to 179 million tonnes, 88% for human consumption, with aquaculture accounting for 52% of the total production and being the primary source of fish for human consumption. FAO (2020) shows that global aquaculture production continued to grow in 2020 amid the COVID-pandemic, although less than from 2018 to 2019. The total production for 2020 consisted of: 87.5 million tonnes of aquatic animals mostly for use as human food, 35.1 million tonnes of seaweeds and other algae for both food and non-food uses.

Fish farming is widespread in Europe, but to date, research and development (R&D) have concentrated on technical aspects of production, and the fragmented landscape of separate disciplines and sectors lacks a more integrative perspective. Scientists and policymakers agree there should be an emphasis on the industry's environmental and social aspects, including greater transparency and traceability. Although product quality is high, product traceability and microbiological safety methods are limited and must be substantially improved to increase consumer confidence and thus uptake. The Eurobarometer of EU consumer habits regarding fishery and aquaculture products (European Union, 2021) reveals that a product's origin is the third most mentioned factor in purchasing decisions after cost.

The EU is also the world's largest importer of fish (24% of the total value of world fish trade), and consumers are generally faced with fish and shellfish of little-known origin, with little information about fishing (gear, feed, welfare issues, processing, and transport), which adds to an already existing issue of lack of trust, especially regarding farmed seafood. Further, EU consumers are keen to have additional information on the fish they buy (e.g., date of catch/harvest, condition of growing), increased by the growing demand by consumers for environmental, ethical, and social information.

These new developments and demands, from science, policy, and consumers side, have brought to light the need to understand the attributes that affect consumers preferences. By planning interventions that foster adherence to consumers demands and the attributes they value when deciding on seafood purchases new business opportunities can materialize. For policy-making it can be an opportunity to promote sustainable consumption and healthy food habits. This is the environment from which FishEUTrust's approach derives.

The goal of FishEUTrust is to defragment the current food system to ensure a sustainable and efficient (e.g. through reduction of bottlenecks/barriers) seafood supply chain by developing solutions to bring about the transparency and traceability needed to promote high-end, pan-European farmed seafood, addressing diet, health, and consumer behaviors as well as sustainable aquaculture and the blue economy.

The innovation at the heart of FishEUTrust is the integration of different stakeholders, actors and consumer sectors in a common platform linking technology providers with supply chain stakeholders engaging directly with socioeconomic analysis informing optimized business models and regulatory/policy actors to co-develop tools, systems and protocols across the seafood value chain intended to increase consumer awareness, engagement, and confidence.

The overarching ambition of FishEUTrust is to develop an integrated approach to increase transparency and consumer trust across the seafood production chain from "Farm-to-Fork". FishEUTrust directly targets Food 2030 and the EU's bioeconomy strategy: (i) addressing nutrition for sustainable and healthy diets, (ii) climate-smart and environmentally sustainable food systems,

(iii) circularity and resource efficiency of food systems and (iv) innovation and empowerment of communities, (v) and creating jobs.

1.1 Scope of the deliverable

This report corresponds to tasks TO1.1, TO1.2 and TO1.3 of the Work Package 1 (WP1) of FishEUTrust. In the scope of WP1, the project is to set up and operationalize five Co-creation Living Labs (CLLs) to link, coordinate and engage key stakeholders according to local specificities and validate CLLs' business approach in conjunction with other WPs.

The deliverable is related to milestone MS1, which is related to the organization of the contextual workshop in Malta. A note on the methodology: there is no single session approaching methodology. Each specific session of the empirical study describes this aspect of the research.

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

This introduction is followed by a theoretical session which introduces the policy scope of the aquaculture in Europe, taking into consideration strategic initiatives and program; an analysis of the Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Legal and Environmental (PESTLE) factors that affect aquaculture industry in the EU; and a discussion on the whole of living labs to foster innovation in the aquaculture sector.

The empirical part of the report describes the outputs related to relevant tasks starting with establishment of FishEUTrust Co-creation Living Labs (CLLs) where the steps for set-up the CLLs are presented including:

- TO1.1: Integrated LLs stakeholder map and analysis (prepared by ABT)
- TO1.2: Establishment of CLLs best practices and operational protocols (prepared by CETGA and REDINN)
- TO1.3: Consolidation of the synergies with the existing network of LLs to implement an inclusive EU-level Web of LLs (prepared by REDINN)

The last chapter is related to Conclusions and recommendations.

2 Theoretical foundations

Aquaculture, the cultivation of aquatic organisms, has become a crucial sector within the European Union (EU), addressing food security, stimulating economic growth, and promoting environmental sustainability. This section offers a comprehensive analysis of the role of aquaculture in European policies and programs, focusing on key objectives, initiatives, challenges, and opportunities. Aquaculture represents a significant segment of the EU's seafood production, strongly focusing on sustainable practices. This means implementing systems and methodologies with minimal negative impacts on local ecosystems while producing seafood efficiently.

2.1 PESTLE Analysis: Aquaculture industry in European context

Aquaculture faces increasing criticism regarding its ecological and social sustainability practices, and the resulting challenges for future innovation processes (Joffre et al., 2017). This is one of the main reasons for the need for adequate assessments of the factors affecting the implementation of aquaculture operations, as well as promoting the improvement of its acceptance by society. This assessment can be done by applying a framework specifying policy, economic, social, technical, legal, and environmental (PESTLE) factors.

The PESTLE framework is an analytical tool used to identify key drivers of change in the strategic environment (Stuiver et al., 2016). According to the Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development (CIPD, online), the PESTLE analysis is a useful tool with a range of applications in strategic business planning, workforce planning, marketing planning, product development, organizational change, and aligning people strategies with the broader organizational strategy. By systematically examining the factors embedded in the PESTLE analysis, it is possible to gain valuable insights into the challenges and opportunities presented by the broader external environment. This analysis aids in making informed decisions, anticipating market trends, and adapting strategies to navigate the dynamic landscape in which an organization operates.

Applying the PESTLE analysis to the European context of aquaculture enables stakeholders in the aquaculture sector to navigate the complex and dynamic external environment. It aids in identifying opportunities for growth, mitigating risks, and aligning strategies with the multifaceted influences shaping the industry.

The following is an outline of the analysis of the European context of aquaculture. This analysis is done to identify the context of operations of the CLLs. In the specific section of the CLL sites, a PESTLE analysis is performed to contextualize the environment where they operate.

To perform a thorough PESTLE analysis, the scrutiny of hundreds of documents would be needed, and the objective here is to show only the most important ones for the sake of space. The European Commission (EC) and the European Parliament have elaborated hundreds of directives and regulations that, when added to the national ones, make it very difficult to identify all the aspects that affect the PESTLE analysis for the operation of LLs in aquaculture. This section refers to the latest directives published by the EC and to the most relevant ones that have been affecting the aquaculture sector since their publication, such as those that have to do with the environment and health. It is worth noting that legislations and policies may affect simultaneously different elements of the PESTLE framework. Even though they are shown here individually by element, this intertwining is necessary to keep in mind.

Two sectoral organizations play a crucial role in bridging aquaculture with the government and public policy arena. The first is the Federation of European Aquaculture Producers (FEAP) (<https://feap.info>), representing the European aquaculture production industry. It serves as the Federation of National Aquaculture Associations in Europe, representing professional fish farming. The second organization is the European Aquaculture and Innovation Platform (EATIP) (<https://eatip.eu>), an international non-profit association dedicated to developing, supporting, and promoting aquaculture, especially in technology and innovation in Europe. EATIP includes all

members of the European aquaculture value chain, from suppliers and producers to processors within the profession. It is accompanied by leading research groups and key representative organizations.

2.1.1 Political factor

Regarding political and legal factors, the aquaculture sector in the EU faces significant challenges related to licensing and the complexity of national systems. These obstacles can hinder growth, particularly affecting small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Political factors are especially intertwined with other elements of the PESTLE framework, as regulations for strategies affect various elements as well. The main strategies that cover growth and sustainability in the EU either mention aquaculture directly or consider this economic activity concerning food security, sustainability, economic growth, and regional sustainable development.

1. **The Blue Growth Strategy:** This ambitious EU plan (EC, 2017) focuses on sustainable growth within the marine and maritime sectors. Aquaculture, as a significant contributor to the blue economy, is central to this strategy. The Blue Growth Strategy envisions a thriving and sustainable marine economy by fostering innovation and sustainable practices in aquaculture.
2. **The EU Green Deal:** As the EU aims to become climate-neutral by 2050, every sector, including fisheries and aquaculture, has a role to play. The Green Deal (EC, 2019a) provides a roadmap for this transition, with initiatives to reduce the carbon footprint and promote sustainable practices across all industries.
3. **Farm to Fork Strategy:** This strategy (EC, 2020) is a component of the Green Deal and focuses on revolutionizing the European food production system. Given the potential of aquaculture as a sustainable protein source, it occupies a significant place in this strategy. The emphasis here is on promoting aquaculture practices that are not only sustainable but also contribute to a healthy and balanced diet for European citizens.
4. **The Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3):** (Foray et al., 2012) is another approach that EU regions can adopt to drive sustainable growth in their respective areas. While not specific to aquaculture, this strategy can be tailored to support innovation and specialization in the marine and maritime sectors. Regions can identify their unique strengths and resources related to aquaculture and develop strategies to enhance competitiveness, promote sustainable practices, and stimulate economic growth in this field. This strategy aligns with the broader objectives of the Blue Growth Strategy and the Green Deal by fostering regional innovation and sustainability efforts.
5. **Circular Bioeconomy:** Circular bioeconomy principles involve the sustainable use of biological resources and waste reduction. In the context of the marine and maritime sectors, this means optimizing the use of marine biomass, minimizing byproducts and waste, and exploring innovative ways to recycle and repurpose materials. Circular economy principles align with the broader sustainability and environmental responsibility goals within these sectors.
6. **Blue Bioeconomy - towards a strong and sustainable EU algae sector:** This initiative (EC, 2022) aims to increase sustainable production, ensure safe consumption, and boost innovative use of algae and algae-based products in Europe.
7. **The Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership (SBEP):** This initiative, co-funded by the EC (SBEP, 2023), provides funding opportunities via regional and national channels that involve the participation of 36 research funding organizations from 23 countries. They are active in the field of innovation and research funding in the blue economy. SBEP's financial endowment amounts to €450 million over 7 years (2021-2027) and involves 60 partners and 25 countries alongside the EC. SBEP's intervention areas can be broken down into five pillars related to aquaculture industry and research operations:
 - Digital Twin of the Ocean at Sub-Sea-Basin Scale
 - Blue Generation Marine Structures
 - Planning and Managing Sea-Uses
 - Healthy "Blue Food" under a "One Health" Approach.
 - Enabling the Green Transition of "Blue Food" Production."

2.1.2 Economic factors

The European Maritime and Fisheries Fund (EMFF) (EC, 2021) is a vital financial instrument supporting the EU's fisheries and aquaculture sectors. It allocates funding to various activities, including modernizing aquaculture facilities, promoting innovation, enhancing environmental sustainability, and improving market access for aquaculture products. The EMFF plays a pivotal role in translating the objectives of the Common Fisheries Policy (CFP), which is presented in the legal factors of the PESTLE analysis, into practical initiatives, contributing significantly to the growth and competitiveness of the aquaculture industry. The EMFF allocates funding to various activities, including:

- **Modernising Aquaculture Facilities:** EMFF provides funding to upgrade and modernise aquaculture facilities. This includes improving infrastructure, adopting new technologies, and enhancing production processes. By supporting modernisation, the EU aims to increase the competitiveness and efficiency of the aquaculture industry.
- **Promoting Innovation:** Innovation is a critical driver in the aquaculture sector. EMFF supports research and development efforts to enhance production techniques, improve disease management strategies, and optimise resource efficiency. Innovation is critical for ensuring the long-term sustainability and growth of the aquaculture sector.
- **Enhancing Environmental Sustainability:** EMFF allocates funds to promote environmental sustainability in aquaculture. This includes projects that focus on reducing the environmental impact of aquaculture operations, such as minimising pollution and mitigating the effects on local ecosystems. Sustainable practices are essential for meeting the EU's environmental objectives.
- **Improving Market Access:** Access to markets within the EU and internationally is crucial for the success of European aquaculture products. EMFF supports initiatives to improve market access, which involves marketing, branding, and promoting European aquaculture products to consumers. It also includes efforts to meet high-quality standards and certifications required for international trade. The EMFF plays a pivotal role in translating the CFP objectives into practical initiatives, contributing significantly to the growth and competitiveness of the aquaculture industry. It aligns with the broader goals of the CFP, such as ensuring sustainability, environmental responsibility, and economic viability in fisheries and aquaculture activities within the EU.

2.1.3 Social factor

The growth and competitiveness of EU aquaculture depend primarily on social acceptance and recognition of its benefits and value, which contemplates three key factors to achieve this acceptance. First, communication on EU aquaculture is important to effectively communicate the benefits and value of EU aquaculture activities and products to increase their acceptance and recognition. Additionally, it requires the integration of EU aquaculture into local communities. In this regard, it may involve working closely with local communities and ensuring aquaculture activities benefit them. Finally, data collection and monitoring are crucial to ensure the sustainability and profitability of EU aquaculture. Furthermore, data can help identify areas for improvement and make informed decisions. These factors are essential to ensure social acceptance and to promote its growth and competitiveness and are included in WP2 of the FishEU Trust project.

The European strategies mentioned in this report favor the social acceptance of aquaculture by reinforcing the sector's contribution to food security and the environmental and social compliance of industrial operations. In the operationalization of the programs into R&I calls, they embed these and other requirements, such as Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), into the guidelines for the proposals.

The study by Cantillo et al. (2021) discusses how EU regulations and guidelines support the social acceptance of aquaculture products by European consumers. Among these, it is important to mention Regulation (EU) No 1379/2013 on the common organization of the markets in fishery and aquaculture products (EC, 2013), and the studies on EU consumer habits regarding fishery and aquaculture products, namely the Eurobarometer (EU, 2018) and the various editions of the EU Fish Market survey.

2.1.4 Technological factors

Knowledge and innovation are key to the development of EU aquaculture. These are promoted through the creation of a cooperation framework that brings together public authorities, industry, researchers, and teachers at both national and regional/local levels. Strategies, guidelines, and legal regulations in this area include the development of innovation clusters for sustainable aquaculture and the promotion of the effective dissemination of research and innovation results to industry end-users and the public, as well as the exploitation of these results.

Various policies and programs mentioned in the political elements of the PESTLE analysis contain funding for the development of technological solutions, knowledge, and innovation in aquaculture. The most important legal guidelines orienting the sector are:

- Regulation (EC) No 470/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 6 May 2009 laying down Community procedures for the establishment of residue limits of pharmacologically active substances in foodstuffs of animal origin, repealing Council
- Regulation (EEC) No 2377/90 and amending Directive 2001/82/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council and Regulation (EC) No 726/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council (OJ L 152, 16.6.2009, p.11).
- Directive 2001/82/EC was referred to as 'pre-mixes' and which are considered in this Regulation as one of the pharmaceutical forms of a veterinary medicinal product for the time up until these products are included in medicated feed or intermediate products
- Directive 2010/63/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 September 2010 on the protection of animals used for scientific purposes
- Regulation (EU) 2016/429 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 9 March 2016 on transmissible animal diseases and amending and repealing certain acts in the area of animal health ('Animal Health Law') (Text with EEA relevance).

As noted, these regulations also impact the legal element of the analysis.

The current framework for Research and Innovation (R&I) funding in the EU, Horizon Europe, provides substantial funding opportunities for aquaculture R&I projects. It supports research endeavors that focus on improving the sustainability, efficiency, and competitiveness of the aquaculture industry. This funding facilitates collaboration among researchers, industry stakeholders, and policymakers to address critical challenges in the sector (EC, 2021b).

2.1.5 Legal factors

The Common Fisheries Policy (CFP) is a cornerstone of the EU's maritime and fisheries management, established to oversee the fisheries and aquaculture sectors within the EU's territorial waters. Its primary objective is to ensure that fishing and aquaculture activities are carried out sustainably and responsibly.

Regulatory Framework: The CFP has its roots in multiple regulations, with the most notable being Regulation (EU) No 1380/2013 (EU, 2013a). This regulation provides a blueprint for managing marine resources, setting quotas, and establishing guidelines for sustainable practices. The CFP incorporates three key pillars:

- **Environmental responsibility:** A central principle of the CFP is the commitment to safeguarding marine biodiversity. This entails regulating and restricting practices such as overfishing and harmful fishing techniques, all geared toward preserving the long-term health of marine species.
- **Economic viability:** While environmental conservation remains a top priority, the CFP also significantly emphasizes the economic sustainability of fisheries and aquaculture. It seeks to strike a delicate balance where these activities can remain economically profitable while adhering to stringent sustainability guidelines.
- **Scientific research:** The reliance on science-based decision-making is at the heart of the CFP. The EU invests in and relies upon marine science research to ensure that policies and regulations are firmly rooted in empirical evidence, enabling effective adaptation to shifting environmental conditions.

2.1.6 Environmental factor

The aquaculture sector is currently grappling with significant challenges posed by climate change, but it holds immense potential to contribute to climate change mitigation and adaptation. In adapting to the effects of climate change, the sector is urged to enhance its resilience, aligning with the guidance provided by the EU's climate change adaptation strategies and national plans. Simultaneously, efforts to minimize the sector's negative contributions to climate change are imperative, necessitating a comprehensive approach to reduce energy consumption and mitigate carbon emissions across production, transport, and processing stages. The main regulations and guidelines related to the environmental compliance of aquaculture sector are:

- Directive 2008/56/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council establishing a framework for community action in the field of marine environmental policy (EC, 2008).
- Managing and protecting Natura 2000 (EC, 2019a) setting the rules and guidance for everyone involved in managing Natura 2000 sites, which includes the legal requirements of national governments, and guidance for local landowners and site managers.
- Habitats Directive Council Directive 92/43/EEC on the conservation of natural habitats and of wild fauna and flora (EC, 1992).

On the energy transition of the EU fisheries and aquaculture sector, the Fisheries and Oceans Pacts Pact towards sustainable, science-based, innovative and inclusive fisheries management (EC, 2023) is the newest reference for guidance.

About funding for environmental R&I, the LIFE Program (2021-2027) (EC, online) is the EU funding instrument for the environment and climate action. LIFE's primary objective is to promote and finance projects that contribute to the implementation, development, and updating of EU environmental and climate policies and laws. It focuses on projects related to environmental conservation, biodiversity protection, climate action, and the transition to a more sustainable and low-carbon economy. It addresses various environmental and climate challenges, including air and water quality, waste management, nature conservation, and adaptation to climate change. Three Sub-Programs support its implementation. They are:

1. **LIFE Nature & Biodiversity:** This sub-program supports projects that aim to conserve and restore natural habitats and species, including Natura 2000 sites, as well as raise awareness about biodiversity. Projects funded under this sub-program may contribute to the conservation and restoration of these habitats, including the protection of water bodies and ecosystems where aquaculture activities are carried out.
2. **LIFE Environment & Resource Efficiency:** This sub-program funds projects that focus on resource efficiency, waste management, and circular economy initiatives, helping to reduce the environmental impact of economic activities. Aquaculture is resource-intensive, requiring water, feed, and energy. Projects under this sub-program that focus on resource efficiency and the circular economy can provide insights and technologies applicable to sustainable aquaculture practices. This includes reducing water usage, optimizing feed formulations, and minimizing waste in aquaculture operations.
3. **LIFE Climate Action:** This sub-program supports projects that contribute to reducing greenhouse gas emissions, promoting climate adaptation measures, and increasing the resilience of communities and ecosystems to climate change. Projects under this sub-program can support initiatives aimed at reducing emissions associated with aquaculture operations. This might involve energy-efficient aquaculture systems, carbon-neutral feed production, or sustainable transportation solutions.

2.2 Living Labs for Innovation in Aquaculture

Aquaculture development has sped up in the last five decades, benefiting from scientific and technological advances that have impacted almost every aspect of aquaculture. Yue and Shen (2022) show how technologies () have increased aquaculture outputs. The authors describe how these technologies have impacted aquaculture operations but emphasize that it is almost

impossible for a single farmer or aquaculture company to integrate these various technologies into different aquaculture systems due to the complexity of the process. They suggest that collaboration among fish farmers, fish scientists, engineers, software developers and economists will help to effectively integrate these technologies into each part of the aquaculture industry to make the industry more sustainable and profitable. Besides these actors, government agencies may supply research funds on multidisciplinary projects while aquaculture extension stations, venture capital and investors may support novel start-ups for integrating disruptive technologies into the aquaculture industry.

As a benefit, the aquaculture industry can become more resource and energy-efficient, as well as generate opportunities for businesses and jobs, including opportunities for women and younger people, therefore giving prospects for adopting inclusive labor policies. Yue and Shen's (2022) view follow the approach to innovation ecosystems, which promotes growth and sustainability for industries and regions.

This approach is in tandem with the view of Joffre et al. (2017). According to them, innovation management strategies incorporating ongoing user feedback could benefit aquaculture research and technology design that feeds into aquaculture innovation. This is especially true when targeting specific groups for greater inclusivity. As a result, these strategies could better facilitate multidirectional interactions between various actors involved in aquaculture systems. To effectively manage the innovation process, this would enhance the integration of institutional, political, economic, and socio-cultural components and aid in elevating the analysis beyond the farm. To further understand the multi-dimensional and multi-level interplays in complex aquaculture systems, the study of aquaculture innovation needs to consider the significant involvement of private sector actors and make better use of systemic methodologies.

Source: Based on Yuen and Shen (2022, p.112)

Figure 1. Technologies applied in aquaculture leading to the rapid increase of aquaculture production in the past 50 years

Living Labs (LL) are a tool to enhance user participation in aquaculture innovation. According to the European Network of Living Labs (ENOLL, n.d.), LLs are open innovation ecosystems that function in real-life environments and use iterative feedback processes throughout a lifecycle

innovation approach to create sustainable impact. LLs focus on co-creation, rapid prototyping and testing and scaling up innovations and businesses, providing (different types of) joint value to the involved stakeholders. LLs foster co-creation and open innovation, engaging the stakeholders of the quadruple helix model of innovation: companies/industry, users/citizens, public organizations/government and researchers/academia (ENOLL, n.d.; Ståhlbröst and Holst, 2012).

Even though ENOLL conceives the Living Labs (LLs) as spaces that engage representatives of the quadruple helix stakeholders (government, academia, industry, and civil society) for co-creation, the approach of FishEU Trust follows the quintuple helix model. This model represents an evolution of the triple helix model (government, industry, academia) and the quadruple helix model, wherein 'the environment or the natural environments represent the fifth helix' (Carayannis et al., 2012)

There have not been theoretical constructions about LLs in aquaculture or aquaculture LLs. To build, even if by approximation, such a characterization of field application of an LL, first constructs of LLs were identified, and then, which field resembles aquaculture the most in terms of operations. In doing so, it was possible to define the most approximate characteristics of an aquaculture LL, which was used to identify LLs in aquaculture in this work.

Westerlund et al. (2018) identified the primary constructs and how they are involved in the operation of LLs and applied them to a case study of 40 LLs applications for ENOLL affiliation. Table 1 shows these constructs, and the results of the case studies are presented in the sequence. Such constructs are helpful for the structuring of LLs.

Table 1. Emergent constructs from living lab cases

Construct	Definition	Scope
Objective	The positive outcome that the innovation output is expected to produce	Collaboration, social impact, business development, user impact, test bed
Governance	A structural or procedural model by which decisions for the innovation projects, process, or organization are made	Managerial process, managerial structure
Openness	Mindset of the organization that is reflected in their level of openness and collaboration	Innovation culture, intellectual property rights
Stakeholders	Entities that add value to the living lab	Participants and their role
Funding	The means by which the living lab financially supports its innovation activities	Public funding, revenue stream of living lab's business model
Values	The benefits the stakeholders gain from their membership and participation within the living lab	Product outcome, social value, business development, validation, resources, networking, knowledge, investment, and marketing.
Communication	The channels, technology, and techniques used to network stakeholders for information exchange	Online presence, media presence, person-to-person interaction
Infrastructure	The necessary resources and specialized equipment required to carry out the innovation activities	Software tools, hardware, sensors, facilities
Methods	The procedural steps used for the inception, development, and deployment of innovation	Attracting participants, ethics, motivational rewards, user support, data collection, idea generation, design, testing, and commercialization.

Source: Westerlund et al (2018, p. 55)

The authors operationalize these constructs accordingly:

Objective: The LL generate innovations through the collaborative work of numerous participants (Collaboration). They form joint operations to handle incubation space, cutting-edge technology, and knowledge databases in a collaborative effort to maximize innovation, reduce expenses, and benefit the ecosystem. Moreover, they venture to enhance regional social impact by promoting citizen engagement, developing technologies that more effectively address needs, and constructing urban infrastructures. The LLs facilitate business expansion for organizations by creating services and resources (e.g., product research, incubation space, market trend analysis, and education). They also encourage entrepreneurialism and employment (economic development), generating comprehensive and individualized solutions and constructing digital infrastructure. LLs ultimately serve as test beds and a structure for conducting experiments and product evaluations in authentic environments alongside users.

Governance: A clear governance structure of LL did not emerge from the cases. Setting the LL's vision, making investment decisions, managing intellectual property, organizing operations, assigning roles, maintaining the LL infrastructures, and planning research are all responsibilities of the governance group. The governance group monitors the performance of the LL to verify that the activities are in line with the intended objectives. They are responsible for administrative and management duties. Additionally, the governing body is accountable for decisions at the project level. By assigning the right individuals to oversee and manage the operations and developing user-centric research approaches, they determine which projects to pursue. In ascending order of prevalence, the legal structures governing living labs are as follows: private, public-private partnership, public-private-people collaboration, undefined, and public.

Openness: In LLs, intellectual property is managed by original equipment manufacturer (OEM), licensing, open source, case-by-case, and legal means, among others. In the consortium agreement, LLs establish guidelines and protocols about the sharing, licensing, and utilization of intellectual property (IP) prior to the commencement of a project. The allocation of benefits and expenses for each participant might be delineated in the agreements, contingent upon their investment and involvement in the advancements. All individuals are required to sign up for this set of regulations. Additionally, LLs may grant their originators (OEM) complete authority over the utilization of the IP or the management of IP for each project among the participating members. To accomplish this innovation and other objectives, collaborative work is fostered within the innovation culture of the LLs. Therefore, LL participants of LLs are guaranteed mutual respect and knowledge exchange. They diminish obstacles by providing unrestricted access to information and implementing open standards to facilitate integration and free tool usage.

Stakeholders: The cases indicated the varied participation of corporations, associations, universities, unions, governments and public bodies, financiers, and civic organizations.

Funding: Government grants and private investments provide most of the funding for LLs. Furthermore, consultancy generates revenue when the LL is paid for services performed to third parties. Because each LL has a different focus, the services provided vary. Consulting services provided by LL include digital marketing, data collection and analytics, training, and product review. Additionally, LLs generate revenue from their work in the form of royalties and sales. However, the members only profit when the products are successfully commercialized. LLs may also rent out their resources, such as facilities and equipment, to third parties for events, lab research, or development.

Value: Members of LLs receive a variety of benefits, including company development, expertise, resources, networking, validation, marketing, social value, and investments. Supportive activities help LL participants reach their business objectives (Business Development). Members benefit from managerial assistance, advisory teams, project development, the experiences/expertise of other members, and education. They get access to the research facilities, incubation space, technology, and knowledge content of the LL and can also form new alliances to get access to new sectors or markets. LLs can hasten the creation of low-cost, high-quality goods and create an

initial market presence by utilizing a standardized method that allows collaborative work (Framework). Their linked activities and ecosystem increase brand awareness and validity for members' companies.

Communication: Two-way communication strives to achieve open discourse for collaborative work in LLs, and it aids in idea generation and gathering input from participants. LLs must also keep members informed of their development and continuing activities. LLs employ communication to brand, legitimate, and achieve public attention. Furthermore, communication technology functions as management tools, such as a database for hosting shared information, managing project activities, and gathering and evaluating ideas.

Infrastructure: Infrastructure requirements for living labs include five types: facilities, networks, hardware, software, and sensors. They consist of dedicated or shared facilities for hosting in-person activities such as events, workshops, and testing in a testbed. Facilities are either owned by the lab or leased to a stakeholder. Servers used to host web technologies and data that promote collaboration are part of the information technology infrastructure (networks). Each lab's hardware, software, and sensors differ depending on their intended function. Sensors, in particular, are employed within the test environment to observe user behavior and gather use statistics.

Methods: Users come to LLs through associations, events, and random sources such as hotspots or housing authorities. The LL informs users of their role and project objectives prior to their participation and obtains written, free agreement. The LL engages users to participate in the project by using lead users as influencers and extrinsic rewards. In addition, the LL provides training and resources. Users and other members debate issues, develop solutions, and establish basic criteria throughout the idea-generation process. Universities and small businesses frequently turn requirements into ideas and prototypes. The solutions are evaluated with users in real-life contexts under the supervision of research professionals, with data acquired via monitoring equipment, digital activity logs, and surveys/interviews. Academics then analyze the data to determine the impact of the remedies. LLs frequently delegate commercialization efforts to firms but may leverage their ecosystem and specialists to promote and adopt ideas

Based on this study Westerlund et al (2018) created a new definition of LL: *“A living lab is a sociotechnical platform with shared resources, collaboration framework, and real-life context, which organizes its stakeholders into an innovation ecosystem that relies on representative governance, open standards, and diverse activities and methods to gather, create, communicate, and deliver new knowledge, validated solutions, professional development, and social impact (p. 57).”*

2.2.1 Living labs in aquaculture

The agriculture and agri-food sectors are the ones with the most resemblance to aquaculture as innovation ecosystems, as well innovation management for agri-food can be an inspiration for aquaculture. According to Asche et al. (2018), aquaculture value chains will become more analogous to those in other agro-industrial sectors as they mature. They propose that the Norwegian salmon sector might achieve significant efficiency by learning from the industrial organization of chicken value chains. They also point out that vertical integration and economies of scale in salmon and chicken production have resulted in significant consolidation among processing and marketing enterprises.

To get an approximation of the similarity of the conceptual application of agri-food LLs to aquaculture, the findings by McPhee et al. (2021), who studied large initiatives from Canada and France and eight other cases from the literature, highlight the unique nature of agroecosystem LLs and their distinct challenges concerning their aims, activities, participants, and context. They emphasize that exceptionally high levels of scientific research characterize agroecosystem LLs, long innovation cycles with high uncertainty due to external factors, and the high number and diversity of stakeholders involved. According to them, agricultural systems are socio-ecological

systems in which power is spread across a network of farmers, consultants, agri-food sector players, local and national governments, and scientists, with the latter dictating innovation. However, like in many other sectors, the agricultural and agri-food sector's innovation flows follow their rhythm and specificities related to four major elements. The first is the link to nature and the living system, which is central to the sector and serves as a shared backdrop and potential for transformation. The importance of "real-world" experimentation cannot be overstated. Second, invention is anchored in a space, region, or location (in the soil). Third, the result (food or energy supply) has a high social value and is a major political priority. Fourth, the agri-food sector's unique and interwoven constellation of institutions, players, and knowledge must be examined because changes influence the entire system and sectoral and national specificities. In transdisciplinary techniques, farmers, scientists, and other interested partners collaborate on co-designing, monitoring, and assessing new and current agricultural practices and technology on working landscapes to promote their efficacy and early uptake (McPhee et al., 2021).

How can the aquaculture LL definition be inspired by the discussion presented by MCPhee et al (2021) which also suffers from the lack of empirical evidence and is bond to little distinction from the general principles common to all LLs? It can start by emphasizing the transdisciplinary approaches involving scientists, fish farmers, fishmongers, aquaculture industry value-chain actors, community and civil society (represented by NGOs and associations), government (especially local municipalities and health and environmental authorities) and other stakeholders in the co-creation, monitoring and evaluation of innovations in fish farming, animal health, consumer engagement and health, environment and others related to the sustainability of the cultivation of fish and seafood.

Deriving a definition for agroecosystem LL from the work of Steen and van Bueren for urban LLs, MCPhee et al (2021) reached the characteristics presented in the central column of Table 2, a proposal is made regarding the characteristics of aquaculture LLs on the third column.

Table 2. The nine defining characteristics of agroecosystem living labs

Dimension	Characteristics of Agroecosystem LLs	Characteristics of Aquaculture LLs
Aims	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aimed at sustainability and resilience of agriculture and agri-food systems • Innovation can be expressed through technology, best management practices, or processes • Knowledge production and knowledge network creation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aimed at sustainability and resilience of aquaculture systems and the natural ecosystem • Innovation can be expressed through technology, best management practices, or processes • Knowledge production and knowledge creation
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exceptionally high level of evaluation and data management • Long/seasonal innovation cycles with high uncertainty due to external factors • Scaling up and out to outcomes at the level of agriculture and agri-food systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High level of evaluation, data management • Long innovation cycles with high uncertainty due to external factors • Scaling up and out to outcomes at the level of aquaculture ecosystems
Participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emphasis on public sector researcher participation • User roles may be diverse and can evolve • Often driven by the public sector or academic institutions • High diversity and number of partners, interests, and values requiring complex governance schemes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emphasis on public sector researcher participation • User roles are related to the position in the value chain • Often driven by the public sector or academic institutions • Diversity and number of partners, interests, and values requiring complex governance schemes
Context	The living lab is embedded within and examined at the scale of agroecosystems	The LL may be totally or partially embedded within and examined at the scale of the aquaculture ecosystem.

Source: Based on MCPhee et al (2021)

Similarly, an emphasis shall be put in the influence of the place-based nature of agroecosystem LLs and the role of place-based innovation, which has drawn on lessons from urban living labs (McPhee et al, 2021), to aquaculture living labs. Following these considerations, the concept of the CLLs implemented by FishEUTrust is introduced.

3 FishEUTrust Co-creation Living Labs

The FishEUTrust project has a very ambitious scope, which is to create or help create and readapt some of the living labs present within the borders of the EU to improve the perception of the end consumer and improve their confidence in fishery and aquaculture products. To this end, it is essential to carry out an in-depth analysis of the needs and capabilities of each of the CLLs that are integrated within this consortium to help them redefine their objectives and identify how to improve their capabilities, both technological, in infrastructure, human or management, to be able to transfer the advances that are being made in the analysis of pollutants, toxins and the control of physicochemical and microbiological parameters in order to integrate them into a programme that is visible to the end consumer, improving confidence in fishery and aquaculture products.

Figure 2. FishEUTrust Co-creation Living Labs concept

The CLLs are conceived as open innovation ecosystems based on a systematic co-creation approach (Figure 2). They support preparatory research, engaging and building an ecosystem of all stakeholders and integrating their expectations to be considered in project stages. CLLs have six main features: (i) active user involvement (target groups); (ii) real-life settings; (iii) testing, validation and demonstration of innovative technologies and solutions; (iv) multi-stakeholder participation and co-creation; (v) business approach and exploitation; (vi) assessment. CLLs actors will cooperate in developing and testing new technologies, products, services, policy instruments, planning tools, organizational forms, and governance arrangements. The network of the CLLs will be a service infrastructure for the project implementation, from the participatory design and review of the competence framework to innovative tools and solutions validation and demonstration to community engagement and dissemination activities.

The project's work begins with a 'start-up' phase, which is initiated by WP1: Establish Co-Creation Living Labs and focuses on the development of the concept for a co-creation process to be applied throughout the project, ensuring that a systemic multi-actor approach is implemented in each development step to collaboratively provide a framework to understand consumer expectations, design innovative products, assess their sustainability, and to demonstrate their benefits. The CLLs are established in partner countries: IPMA (Portugal), CETGA (Spain), ABT (Malta), Bugenvila (Croatia) and OXY (Denmark), covering three different areas, Mediterranean, Atlantic and North Sea, integrating across all sectors of the value chain to support the development, test and validation of the FishEUTrust deliverables. At the same time, it should be mentioned that PT, ES, MT and DK have the highest consumption rate of fish in EU. The CLLs covers aquaculture (IPMA, CETGA, ABT), gastronomy sector (Bugenvila) and industrial partner developing aquafarm systems and control technologies (OXY).

The CLLs locations (Figure 3) have been chosen based on the different areas in which aquaculture is developed in the EU, not only because of the geographical differences, but also because of the differences in temperatures and species that can be farmed in each of them, trying to represent most of the species farmed in the European Union.

Source of the map: Vector Sock (online)

Figure 3. Location of FishEUTrust CLLs

The set-up of the five FishEUTrust CLLs follows the steps presented in Figure 4. The first three steps are described in detail as part of this deliverable.

Identification of Stakeholders (TO1.1)	The stakeholder maps have been provided in T1.1 The leader of each LL has identified the local actors that may be interested in the project according to the Quintuple Helix model
Establishment of CLLs best practices and operational protocols (TO1.2)	Preparation of several questionnaires to identify their interest, availability and categorized base don their role in the FishEUTrust project SWOT and PESTEL analysis Organization of Pilot Contextual Analysis workshop
Consolidation of the synergies with the existing network of LLs (TO1.3)	Implementation of the best practices in the CLLs Develop the international web of LLs and identify cross-pollination potential
Webpage for the CLL and dissemination material (WP8)	A page for the CLLs was prepared and designed on the FishEUTrust webpage (www.fisheustrust.eu) Dissemination material will be designed to be used by the pilot areas to advise the CLLs activities to communicate the objectives of the CLLs to interested actors
Demonstration activities – Active involvement (WP2-WP7)	Provide support in co-creation as a validation and demonstration sites of social-economic principles and innovative technology Participation in the FishEUTrust activities throughout the duration of the project
Engagement activities (WP8)	Participation in the FishEUTrust activities throughout the duration of the project Prepare the plan and activities for the engagement with relevant stakeholders: organization of awareness campaigns
Evaluation	A monitoring and evaluation system design from the launch of CLLs and its applied during and after each involvement activities Overall evaluation of the CLLs included in project reports

Figure 4. Steps to set-up FishEUTrust CLLs

4 FishEUTrust Stakeholders Mapping

The output of this stakeholder mapping is the integrated map of stakeholders, target groups and sectors that may influence or be influenced by the project. The main activities in this task were to co-construct a stakeholder map with pilot teams (interpreted to mean LLs), identify stakeholders according to the quintuple helix model, which contemplates organizations linked to academia, industry, government, civil society and environment, and compare and contrast stakeholders in each pilot CLL to prepare digital solutions for promotion and consumer empowerment strategies (undertaken in different WPs and tasks of the project). In detail, the methodology used to identify, analyze and map the project's different stakeholders is presented, along with the results and analysis of the stakeholder mapping task and the challenges and lessons learned.

4.1 Methodology

The stakeholder mapping methodology was adapted from the Deliverable DTP3_732_2.2 of the Interreg Danube Transnational Programme ISTER Project (2021). The methodology is broken into two major sections, context of stakeholders and application of stakeholder methods. Different tools were used during the identification and analysis of stakeholders, and these are described below.

The initial step was to contextualize and identify stakeholders directly and indirectly related to the project. This is essential to create an impact and reach a larger audience, with a special focus on diversity, inclusivity, and equality and ensuring the inclusion of different actors from all aspects of the quintuple helix model of education, industry, government, public and environment. Key stakeholders should be identified based on the key messages, goals, and outcomes of the project.

Some examples important to consider are:

- Living Labs
- Supply chain solutions
- Interoperable seafood traceability practices
- Cultural and culinary heritage
- Consumer behaviour
- Sustainable, healthy, traceable wild and farmed seafood
- Unified and standardized frameworks

One of the tools used to identify stakeholders was a questionnaire, which compiled a list of questions aiming to set up a guide for potential stakeholder consideration by each of the CLL coordinator partners.

- Who will be affected by FishEUTrust project activities?
- Who will be able to influence the outcomes of the project?
- What partnerships might build around the issues involved?
- Whose voices or interest on the subject might not be heard?
- Who will be the end users of the project outcomes?
- Who are the most vulnerable among the potentially impacted, and are special engagement efforts necessary?

Based on the outcomes of the questionnaire, the was created with the aim to identify and analyse stakeholders using different criteria.

Source: Adapted from the ISTER Project (2021)

Figure 5. FishEUTrust strategy for stakeholder mapping

Table 3. Criteria for the identification of stakeholders

Topic	Information requested
Description	Name of the stakeholder <i>Short description</i> Role in the value chain i.e., fish farmer, seafood distributor etc. <i>Stakeholder Group referring to the quintuple helix</i> Key contacts & contact details <i>Country and/or LL: Country that the organization operates in and/or the country of the LL this stakeholder is relevant to</i> Main activity in CLL: Description of the main activity or role that the stakeholder will undertake as part of the CLL
Interest & Influence	Depending on the stakeholder expertise and projected interest in the project and influence both over the project and outwardly towards other stakeholders (low, medium, or high). <i>Project aspects likely to be of interest to the Stakeholder: Which of the specific objects, key exploitable results or values of the project will the stakeholder be most interested in.</i> How the stakeholder may influence/be impacted by FishEUTrust: In which ways may the stakeholder be impacted by the project or be able to influence the outcomes of the project. <i>Regional interest & influence: Described in the above interest & influence, however, specified to the region or CLL of relevance rather than the whole project.</i>
For engagement	Key messages from FishEUTrust to this stakeholder: Which messages from the project need to be shared with the stakeholder. <i>Suggested for of motivation or engagement: Potential engagement strategy or ideas foreseen to interact with this stakeholder. i.e., workshop, survey, general awareness etc.</i>
Networks	Key relationships with other stakeholders: Indication of relationships with other stakeholders within the list, relationship to be exploited by specific project activities. <i>Involvement in other networks or projects: Other networks or projects stakeholders are involved in which may be of relevance to FishEUTrust.</i>
Environmental Interests	Environmental interests and goals of the stakeholder, could include which SDG14 targets the stakeholders are contributing to.
Partner	Information on stakeholder contributed by which partner.

The information provided in the stakeholder list influenced the creation of the interest and influence matrix and overall maps for the project. It also provides inspiration for the engagement activities of the CLLs and other WPs and activities directed towards interacting with stakeholders i.e., WP2 and 8. The stakeholder list mapped 471 entries.

Figure 6. Participants at Contextual workshop in Malta

Implementing collaboration with the sister project Sea2See (Innovative Blockchain Traceability Technology and Stakeholders’ Engagement Strategy for Boosting Sustainable Seafood Visibility, Social Acceptance and Consumption in Europe) in the mapping of stakeholders, a joint workshop was organized in December 2022. The FishEUTrust mapping integrates existing stakeholder maps (EuroFIR) and include the needs of other WPs, mainly WP2 and WP3. ABT organized a contextual workshop in

Malta on 2-3 February 2023 (pictured in Figure 6) to discuss possible mapping and need in collaboration with CLLs.

4.2 Interest and influence matrix

The level of interest and influence defined during the stakeholder list creation was used to define the interest and influence matrices (Figure 7). The matrices are dependent on the level of interest or influence a stakeholder has in or on the project will determine whether they are considered a core stakeholder for future engagement practices or if they are to be kept informed of the project and outcomes but not involved specifically in any of the activities. Stakeholders identified with high interest and influence are placed in the top right of the matrix, in the blue section.

Figure 7. Interest and influence matrix

Stakeholders with high interest and low influence or vice versa were placed in the corresponding green section, this also included stakeholders with medium interest and/or influence. Stakeholders identified with low influence and interest are placed in the yellow section. These sections are a precursor to the mapping stage of the process. All stakeholder in the blue section form the core stakeholders, the stakeholders in the green sections form the second-circle and the stakeholders in the yellow section form the third circle.

Stakeholders identified with high interest and influence are placed in the top right of the matrix, in the blue section. Stakeholders with high interest and low influence or vice versa were placed in the corresponding green section, this also included stakeholders with medium interest and/or influence. Stakeholders identified with low influence and interest would be placed in the yellow section. These sections are a precursor to the mapping stage of the process. All stakeholder in the blue section form the core stakeholders, the stakeholders in the green sections form the second-circle and the stakeholders in the yellow section form the third circle.

A range of different mapping strategies, as utilized in the ISTER project, were investigated during the course of this task but all with limitations in regard to the number and specificities of the stakeholders mapped and the relationships among them. As well, several different software and tools were explored for the creation of the stakeholder maps. These included, but were not limited to Lucidchart, Smaply, Gephi, Miro Board and Borealis. Unfortunately, there was a limited number of appropriate software available, especially those that did not require an existing knowledge of coding, allowed for integration of large quantities of data, and that took budget into consideration. Miro Board was decided upon as it provided the most flexibility to explore different options in visualization, however, as previously mentioned, there were issues in mapping of relationships between stakeholders. Upon review of the other available software, this would have presented as an issue while using most of them, especially with big datasets. Other issues identified with the

other potential software was a large focus was built around engagement of the stakeholders which in the remit of the FishEUTrust project falls into the scope of other tasks and work packages.

4.3 Maps

All partners were asked to populate the stakeholder list which in turn informed the initial maps of the project. The maps generated for the whole project are too large to be contained within this document. As of the date of writing there are seven main maps, these are: a map for each of the five CLLs; a map of stakeholders in the Mediterranean and in Northern Europe (including the UK). The stakeholders were also grouped by their position in the value-chain, following the representation in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Value chain stakeholders map

4.4 Analysis

The total number of stakeholders contributed to the list 471 by November 2023, as the execution of the project evolves, the number may increase. Under the quintuple helix categories, a majority of the stakeholders identified fell into the industry category followed by governance (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Number of stakeholders identified under each quintuple helix category

The largest gaps were in the environmental category, and it has been noted there were problems in identifying environmental stakeholders. The stakeholders were also categorized by their role in the value chain at a high level, both directly involved and in ancillary roles. Of the stakeholders identified at a high level directly involved in the value chain 49 were identified in fisheries/aquaculture, 46 were involved in retail and 42 involved in long/short chain transport (Figure 10). Of the stakeholders identified in high level ancillary roles to the value chain, 90 were identified as government or governmental bodies, 88 of the identified were associations or NGOs and 80 as science and research institutions (Figure 11).

Figure 10. Stakeholders in the value chain

Figure 11. The distribution of stakeholders outside the value chain

Stakeholders were also identified by different roles, both in and outside of the value chain, of which seafood exporters government departments contributed to the greatest number closely followed by fish farmers (Figure 12). It should be noted here that some of the stakeholders fell into multiple roles within the value chain and may contribute to more than one column.

Figure 12. Number of identified stakeholders in each role of the value chain

The country with the highest number of identified stakeholders is Malta followed by Portugal and Italy. It must be noted here that some of the stakeholders operate across multiple countries and therefore contributed to more than one column. Of the living lab countries, Croatia had 9 identified stakeholders, Denmark had 14, Malta had 53, Portugal had 50 and Spain had 38 (Figure 13). This indicates that some countries may need to identify further stakeholders to be able to undertake ample stakeholder engagement activities, especially regarding targeting each aspect of the quintuple helix model.

Figure 13. Number of stakeholders identified for each CLL

The list of stakeholders is likely to develop throughout the life of the project as CLLs and other partners begin their engagement activities and further develop networks related to the outcomes and achievements of the project. The maps have been developed in a way that allows for them to be altered to any changes in relationships with stakeholders and can be created for any specific needs that arise within the project.

5 Establishment of FishEUTrust Co-creation Living Labs: Best practices and protocols

One of the current main challenges for the formation but also longevity /sustainability of LLs is the absence of a shared understanding of what constitutes a LL, the diverse range of practices and concepts essential for their creation and implementation, and the difficulty individuals encounter in recognizing the value derived from their involvement in the co-creation process. The multitude of roles and participant types, including those from public administration and citizens, adds complexity to the landscape of innovation practices within LLs. Against this background, capacity-building is needed for the understanding of what constitutes LLs and how they are to be governed and maintained.

5.1 Methodology

To create capacity building for establishing the CLLs, the partner coordinators participated in training activities run by REDINN in the scope of WPI monthly meetings. In those meetings, the coordinators were introduced to the concepts of LLs according to the ENoLL methodology and discussed their own CLL operational context. A protocol to initiate the implementation of the CLLs was elaborated by REDINN and shared with the CLL coordinators.

Two steps were performed to analyze, understand, and mobilize the operating conditions (i.e., location, logistics, equipment, human and financial services) necessary to set up the CLLs: the presentation of the CLLs and a questionnaire (Annex 1). The CLLs were described according to the template provided by REDINN, including the following points: Overview, Services carried out by LL, Core Stakeholders, Living Lab objectives, Project-specific objectives, SWOT analysis, and Sustainability plan for LL after the project ends.

The prepared questionnaire in Annex 1 includes thirty questions covering the PESTLE analysis's political, economic, social, technological, legal and environmental elements. The thirty questions were agreed upon among the project partners and aimed to achieve a view of the capacities and shortcomings of each of the CLLs concerning the objectives set in the FishEUTrust project. This questionnaire provided a picture of the CLLs and the situation of the aquaculture industry in each country where the LLs are present. Based on the CLLs' answers, a PESTLE and SWOT analysis for each CLLs was performed. Notably, not all questions were analyzed in this report as they will serve as input for further project activities.

To discuss the role and implementation of CLLs in the FishEUTrust project, a Pilot Contextual Analysis workshop was organized on October 9 in Florence, Italy, according to the agenda presented in Table 4 and pictured in Figure 14.

Table 4. Contextual analysis workshop held in Florence on 9 October 2023

Time	Plenary Session	Facilitator
16:30-16:40	Introducing the workshop	REDINN
16:40-17:30	Presentations by the CLLs	
10'	ABT, Malta	ABT
10'	CETGA, Spain	CETGA
10'	IPMA, Portugal	IPMA
10'	Bugenvila, Croatia	Bugenvila
10'	OXY, Denmark	OXY
17:30-18:30	Discussion What are the challenges faced by the CLL and how to tackle them? How can the CLL share knowledge and experiences among themselves? What are the next steps for the implementation of the CLLs? How to monitor the progress of the CLLs?	REDINN
18:30	Closing	

Figure 14. Active discussion at the Pilot Contextual Analysis workshop

After the presentation the discussion has been initiated between CLLs. It was possible to identify the specific interest of the CLLs in relation to FishEUTrust project and seafood supply chain (Figure 15).

Figure 15. Identification of FishEUTrust CLLs in the seafood supply chain

5.2 FishEUTrust Co-creation Living Labs implementation protocol

FishEUTrust CLLs are fine-tuned with the project's aim to defragment the current food system to ensure a sustainable and efficient seafood supply chain by developing solutions to bring about the transparency and traceability needed to promote high-end, pan-European farmed seafood, addressing diet, health, and consumer behaviors as well as sustainable aquaculture and the blue economy. They are being established with the aim to:

- Engage citizens and industrial stakeholders
- Foster uptake of seafood, namely farmed-based seafood
- Maximize consumer experience
- Validate health benefits through seafood
- Relate health benefits to high standards of quality, safety and traceability

Quality, safety, traceability and sustainability of the CLLs operations and outputs are to be secured by specific approach covering each one of the dimensions, following Table 5 representation.

Table 5. FishEUTrust CLLs' approach to quality, safety, traceability and sustainability of farmed fish and seafood

Dimension	FishEUTrust approach
Quality	Fish/shellfish quality in aquaculture has two main vectors: nutritional and sensory. The quality of water and feed combined with the welfare of the animals are key contributors to both vectors.
Safety	The control of the feed, water composition, and the guarantee that no illegal medicines are administered to cultivated organisms (at any stage of their development), as well as the inexistence of drug residuals in the edible portion of fish/shellfish are critical conditions that require monitoring in order to demonstrate CLL safety. Integrated smart control systems based on sensor technologies to monitor freshness and presence of pathogens, antibiotics and biotoxins along the seafood supply chain will be developed.
Traceability	Traceability can be demonstrated by the feasibility and reliability of genomics, metabolomics and isotope analysis tools and may encompass all material flows in an aquaculture system. Further digital technologies for traceability based on Product Passport and/or Blockchain will be developed.
Sustainability	A crucial dimension of the CLLs must be the demonstration of the sustainability of fish/shellfish production. For instance, Recirculating Aquaculture Systems may contribute to this goal. Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture combining different trophic levels: seaweed production, shellfish/sea urchin/other seaweed grazers, and fish (predator) also favors sustainability.

Considering that the FishEUTrust CLLs are being implemented at different paces in different areas, a simple guide was created to be used as a protocol to support the local implementation of the CLLs. It is necessary to consider that within the selected CLLs countries (Spain, Croatia, Portugal, Malta and Denmark), there is local context with less established food and fish-related networks, and for the project, this could be an opportunity as well. FishEUTrust has the chance to play a greater role in shaping the network of stakeholders.

5.2.1 The multi-actor network approach

There are many commonalities between LLs and the multi-actor approach implemented under FishEUTrust. The approach to innovation applied by the CLLs included systematically:

- user-centered innovation, empowering fishermen and fish farmers to be on the driving seat of innovation;
- assembling several types of knowledge, skills and competencies to solve the problem identified or answer to the needs of the wild fishermen and fish farmers into joint innovation;
- activities with up and downstream “industry” and “policy makers” also frequently present;
- collecting research and innovation needs from practice;
- co-creation of knowledge and solutions.

The most suitable configuration for FishEUTrust CLLs must include all the quintuple helix actors (Government, Industry, Public, Academia, Environment) within the local context, so they should be interconnected with each other and the CLLs. The rationale behind the need to have all the representatives of the quintuple helix involved in each of the CLLs is that every CLL should relate to one of the three geographic areas that the FishEUTrust project considers, especially since each of these geographic areas might have particular features in terms of stakeholders' response to the inputs to which they are exposed.

The governance of the CLLs might be facilitated by selecting of no more than 3 or 4 profiled stakeholder representatives for every category in every country.

5.2.2 Implementation of the local CLLs

The CLL coordinators shall build the stakeholder networks in their local context. To do so, the CLLs activities should consider the following phases:

1. **Actor/stakeholder identification and mobilization based on the FishEUTrust visioning:** This first phase involves the relevant actors within each CLL. It involves developing and aligning visions and understanding barriers and opportunities to increase trust in farmed seafood and fish products.
2. **Agenda setting:** Phase two involves the transformation of the agendas of every stakeholder by developing and identifying showcases and initiatives able to contribute to change in the level of trust in seafood, making it more sustainable and resilient.
3. **Implementing the vision:** The third phase involves putting into practice the CLLs' visioning agendas, engaging in the prototyping and piloting of innovative (social) experiments, including serious games, which will be developed in WP7.
4. **Scaling up and continuity:** FishEUTrust CLLs should expand across Europe its vision for the amelioration of trust in farmed fish and seafood for a healthy and sustainable diet, also thanks to its instruments (Tools and IT Platform) developed by the project, which will be distributed and exploited.

To support the engagement of stakeholders and the design of the operations of the CLLs, a structure answering to the following questions might be helpful:

- WHO is interested (Stakeholder)
- WHEN is interested (Timing of actions)
- WHY should be interested (Objective)
- HOW could be interested (Channel)
- WHAT is interesting (Message)

Answering these questions is the starting point to achieve the goal of involving stakeholders because they will help to design a clear statement (e.g. *"Design with us your social, economic and environmental friendly seafood future"*) to be used in inviting them, which can be done by e-mail or with the support of social media to be defined based on answers to the above questions, for an event in a suitable format for a co-creation session.

Careful planning must be devoted to the organization of the events. There should be consideration regarding the stakeholders already involved in projects or other activities with the CLL coordinating organization, the type of stakeholder to be engaged and their needs and the types of events to engage them with, amongst others. When a list of potential stakeholders has been identified and the stakeholders have confirmed their participation to the event, as a global strategy it is possible to apply the following:

- Listen to their presentation and understand who they are and what they want to do or propose (interview).
- Formally engage them and decide who is the stakeholder that best aligns with the FishEUTrust project goal.
- Integrate stakeholders' input into the project, make sure to have plans for what comes next, and ensure stakeholders know what to expect.

5.2.3 Responsible Research and Innovation in the implementation framework

The CLLs shall follow the Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) principles in Table 6 and set up a participatory research agenda.

For RRI to take place, it is necessary to bring together and align a wide range of actors and activities. All stakeholders shall be involved in the R&I practice and share responsibility for the outcomes. **CLLs coordinators must be open and adaptive to change their approach and behavior in the face of stakeholders' needs.**

Table 6. Responsible research and innovation principles

	Diverse & inclusive: involve a wide range of actors and the public early in R&I practice, deliberation, and decision-making to yield valuable, high-quality knowledge. This act will strengthen democracy and broaden sources of expertise, disciplines, and perspectives.
	Anticipative & reflective: envision impacts and reflect on the underlying assumptions, values, and purposes to better understand how R&I shapes the future. This action will yield valuable insights and increase our capacity to act on what we know.
	Open & transparent: communicate in a balanced, meaningful way methods, results, conclusions, and implications to enable public scrutiny and dialogue. This action benefits the visibility and understanding of R&I.
	Responsive & adaptive to change: modify modes of thought and behavior, overarching organizational structures, in response to changing circumstances, knowledge, and perspectives. Such modifications will align with the needs of stakeholders and the public.

Source: RRI Tools (online)

In the sequence, the FishEUTrust CLLs are described with the information available to date, noting that they are in the implementation phase. A contextual analysis, considering a PESTLE and a SWOT analysis, was performed for each site.

5.3 FishEUTrust Co-creation Living Labs

5.3.1 [AquaBioTech \(ABT, Malta\): Traceability](#)

Background: AquaBioTech Group (ABT) is an independent aquaculture, fisheries, biotechnology and environmental testing/research, engineering, consulting, development, and training company with its own dedicated research and marine survey facilities. ABT operates globally, specializing in three main areas:

- Aquaculture and fisheries consultancy from resource management and market research to policy development and feasibility, due diligence studies;
- Contracted aquaculture research for feed development, pharmaceutical testing and breeding programmes;
- Design and commissioning of land-based and marine aquaculture production systems and technologies

Infrastructure: ABT has its own independent, biosecure and fully licensed land-based, recirculating aquaculture facilities based in Malta (ABTInnovia) where the company uses its proprietary recirculation aquaculture technology (ExperiRAS™) to deliver aquaculture nutrition, technology and vaccine research, development, and testing services. The facility consists of forty-eight individual trial systems contained within thirty-one biosecure wet lab trial rooms with full monitoring and control of environmental parameters. The facilities are supported by Good Laboratory Practice (GLP) certified laboratories where water quality and ecotoxicology trials, corrosion and biofouling efficacy testing can be performed. ABT activities also include apparatus for research in water management and nutrient reuse of aquaculture effluents. ABT operates in compliance with the requirements of Good Manufacturing Practice (GMP) with respect to biological testing of fish vaccines and vaccine intermediates.

ABT in FishEUTrust: The infrastructure facilities can be used to integrate/test the new tools being developed within the scope of the project – both through the production of research-grade fish or through connection with a unique network of industry-based stakeholders willing to provide samples and information that can be used in the testing of the project tools. ABTs laboratory facilities allow for sample collection and in-house testing to be undertaken within the scope of the project. The facility also has fully supported offices, meeting and training rooms to facilitate stakeholder workshops and training activities. Thus, the following activities are foreseen:

- Provision of samples – all relevant tools being created as part of the project will be used during this activity (WP4 and WP5).

- Test three tools and 3 sensors in potential collaboration with industry partner.
- Provision of the relevant data (WP2, WP3, WP6, WP7).
- Engagement Workshops/Events (WP8): all tools will be demonstrated and showcased during engagement workshops/events with the public, industry and education sectors. It is planned to organize one awareness campaign, participate in five stakeholder engagement activities per year, present FishEUTrust at five communication dissemination events per year.
- Increase visibility of FishEUTrust: 100 followers in the first year of Malta CLL LinkedIn activation and 400 followers on Malta CLL LinkedIn by end of project
- Co-creation Workshops (WP1): Promote/develop tool concepts with the wider industry to ensure they answer the challenges/needs identified.
- Tentative – Potential to engage a local aquaculture producer to allow for the testing of tools along the whole supply chain.

Relevant stakeholders: main stakeholders related to the Malta CLL are from the civil society, government, industry and academia and universities.

	People, consumers	Malta Chef's Society, Malta Hotels & Restaurants Association, Eat Fresh Fish Malta
	Government Policy makers	Food Agency Malta, Ministry for Sustainable Development, Environment and Climate Change, Department of Fisheries and Aquaculture, Ministry of Health, Ministry of Education
	Industry, SMEs	Azzopardi Fisheries, Fish4tomorrow, Malta Fish Farming Ltd.
	Academia University	Institute of Tourism Studies, University of Malta, WestMED National Hub Malta,

Contextual analysis: PESTLE & SWOT: PESTLE and SWOT analysis for Malta CLL are presented in Tables 7 and 8, respectively.

Table 7. PESTLE analysis for ABT CLL.

Political	Economic	Socio-cultural
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Frequent representation at public/scientific dissemination events and fairs. • CLL has not been able to identify Maltese environmental stakeholders so far. • Well-established network of Maltese stakeholders, especially industry-based. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There are no national or European funding programs that support LL activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opportunity to develop relationships in other areas of the supply chain • Consumers are unwilling to give data for our survey. They might not want to participate in our data collection about their seafood habits. • Maltese consumers have low seafood consumption. • Minimal relationships in the rest of the supply chain. • Consumers are unwilling to give data for our survey.
Technological	Legal	Environmental
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical knowledge of the aquaculture and fisheries industries. • No technological developments specific to the living lab so rely on promoting those developed by partners • Database available for quintuple helix 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food safety standards are not something we are familiar with, but Malta does follow EU legislation • Aquaculture farms are often under specific environmental legislation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There are environmental regulations that inform the licensing and regular operation of aquaculture farms

Table 8. The SWOT analysis for ABT CLL

Strength	Weakness
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Well-established network of Maltese stakeholders, especially industry-based. • Technical knowledge of the aquaculture and fisheries industries. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No technological developments specific to the living lab, so promote those developed by partners.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Frequent representation at public/scientific dissemination events and fairs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Very focused on production aspects of the supply chain with minimal relationships with the rest of the supply chain to engage with. No identified environmental stakeholders in Malta.
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Small and tight-knit aquaculture industry with room for digitalization and traceability development Opportunity to develop relationships in other areas of the supply chain. Youth are open to learning about sustainable seafood practices. New calls, projects and initiatives involving LLs – which can contribute to the long-term sustainability of the CLL. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Industry may not be interested in sharing data with outsiders. Consumers are unwilling to give data for our survey. Maltese consumers have low seafood consumption. No wild seabream for samples.

5.3.2 CETGA (Spain): Fish Health

Background: CETGA CLL focuses on the analysis and development of tools for the sanitary control and biosecurity of all aquaculture production, as well as testing, analyzing and controlling the contaminants that may be present in the water. Another activity is to develop technologies that improve animal welfare and the sustainability of aquaculture production, all of which is transferred to the aquaculture sector and society through workshops, seminars and the media. CETGA has the capacity to develop, research and manufacture vaccines and treatments that allow the control and eradication of microorganisms that may be a threat to agricultural production, it also has laboratories and a pilot plant that allows testing and evaluating newly developed technologies and products that can facilitate and improve aquaculture production.

CETGA in FishEUTrust: A living CLL will generate knowledge when raising aquaculture animals, such as knowing first-hand the symptoms of pathologies and preventing them on farms. The main activities within FishEUTrust include providing fish and mussels, samples for genomic, metagenomic and stable isotope analysis. Testing the smart tools developed to determine bacteria, antibiotics, toxins, and freshness will also be possible. They will also organize an awareness campaign and contribute the data for the business models.

Relevant Stakeholders: The management and coordination of CETGA's activities is directed by the aquaculture industry, which comprises all the positions on its board of directors. On a second level, CETGA interacts with society, administrations and universities through meetings and encounters in which sensitivities towards the aquaculture sector and products are asked.

	People, consumers	Fish & food consulting, Salud Comunidad de Madrid
	Government Policy makers	GENCAT (Generalitat de Catalunya, Administration of Catalonia), Institute of Health Carlos III, Regional Government of Andalusia (Junta de Andalucía)
	Industry, SMEs	NuevaPescanova, Stolt Sea farm, Avramar, Profand, Culmarex, Flatantic
	Academia University	El Centro Tecnológico Naval y del Mar, IATA (CSIC), AZTI- Ciencia y tecnología marina y alimentaria, URV (University Rovira & Virgili)

Contextual analysis: PESTLE & SWOT: PESTLE and SWOT analysis for CETGA CLL are presented in Tables 9 and 10, respectively.

Table 9. PESTLE analysis for CETGA CLL in Spain

Political	Economic	Socio-cultural
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CETGA is a valid interlocutor of the sector with the government for matters related to aquaculture. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CETGA funding is private and the activity as a living lab has to be funded by CETGA partners. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Communication with consumers is scarce. Consumer demands or needs are obtained through supermarkets

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CETGA is a partner of European associations such as EATIP or FEAP, which are interlocutors with the European Commission on aquaculture issues. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There are competitive European or national funds. EMFAF is an opportunity to improve project financing. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The relationship with environmental associations is difficult because many of them are not in favour of aquaculture development.
Technological	Legal	Environmental
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CETGA has a live fish laboratory to test products such as vaccines or probes in fish or molluscs. It has microbiological and chemical analysis laboratories. CETGA has a pilot plant with a stock of brood stock. Designs and manufactures autovaccine and monoclonal antibodies. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In Spain, the farms following the Spanish rules copied and pasted from EU directives and rules, but the market demands higher standards than the farms must accomplish. Reports are needed from multiple organizations and society, causing paralysis of years or decades in the administrative procedures for any new aquaculture activity. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Environmental reports are needed from multiple organizations and society, causing paralysis of years or decades in the administrative procedures for any new aquaculture activity.

Table 10. SWOT analysis for CETGA CLL

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 75% of aquaculture production is within CETGA. Collaboration with universities. Legal area that advises companies in their bureaucratic procedures. Area de R&D Pilot farm. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Poor image of the aquaculture sector in a part of society limits our growth. Distant location of cities is a problem to hire researchers.
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fish consumption increases so aquaculture grows. There is a high demand for the services developed by CETGA <p>EMFAF is an opportunity to improve project financing.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High running costs Being close to the sea. There is an environmental regulation that may be incompatible with our activity.

5.3.3 OXY (Denmark): Data provider

Background: OxyGuard (OXY) was founded with the primary objective to create equipment tailored to users' needs. Products include scientifically validated measuring, monitoring and control systems for aquaculture. We tailor products and develop futureproof equipment with the primary goal to promote the success of our customer's fish farms. We are also actively involved with bringing the aquaculture industry to the next level of development – the industry 4.0 (digitalization).

OXY in FishEUTrust: The prime scope for this CLL is to demonstrate the future digital farm and integration of data in the value chain. It will make collected data available for marketing, the consumers, and the whole value chain. The CLL is a place to integrate at least three links in the value chain. Collecting digital information is based on on-farm sensors giving online data for important water quality parameters. Furthermore, employees will be able to enter data about manual actions. Data on the environmental impact of farming will be accessible, and it will be the process industry and the buyer/wholesaler/retailer who will finally decide which data will be expedient to present to consumers. The development of data transfer between the links will be important, and it is expected that it will be necessary to look more closely at standards for data transfers. The type and value of the data must also be decided upon, and testing and validation will occur when the equipment is in place. Eventually, wholesales and consumers can be involved, which shall be coordinated by another entity, not by OXY itself, for being primarily an equipment and data supplier.

Relevant Stakeholders: The stakeholders of the CLL are the industry, business associations and universities.

	People, Consumers	Danish Food Informatics https://www.danfood.info/index.asp
	Government, Policy makers	DVFA (The Danish Veterinary and Food Administration), ICES (International Council for the Exploration of the Sea), Eurofish
	Industry, SMEs	Aller Aqua (feed producer), DanAqua (fish farms), Dansk Akvakultur, Food & Bio Cluster Denmark
	Academia, University	DTU-Aqua, National Institute of Aquatic Resources, DTU-FOOD, National Food Institute

Contextual analysis: PESTLE & SWOT: PESTLE and SWOT analysis for OXY CLL are presented in Tables 11 and 12, respectively.

Table 11. PESTLE analysis for OXY CLL in Denmark

Political	Economic	Socio-cultural
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> One way to implement transparency and ultimately, the consumers trust in the aquaculture industry is through political will, and making it necessary for producers to supply the needed data, throughout the value chain. The bureaucracy in Denmark is a great barrier to expand aquaculture. The legal-framework is diverse and 'a one-stop-shop' for aquaculture does not exist. Shifting governments alter the strategies every four year. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Danish living lab funding is private and the activity as a living lab must be funded by private sector. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High engagement with the industry. Traceability and transparency of all data to the society. One of the main challenges will be convince the Danish aquaculture sector to use the system from the CLL and collect the necessary data from the value chain, forth until it reaches the consumer.
Technological	Legal	Environmental
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water quality sensors, cloud-based aquaculture production management platform (Cobália). Manual recording (mortality, feed administered, vaccines, auxiliary chemicals used etc.). Future possibilities: Automatic feeding, development of algorithms to present, e.g., CO₂/kg fish produced, kWh/kg fish produced, feedback from the processor (report of slaughtering), processor to be able to quickly get an overview of biomass available for slaughtering at the farms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The strict legalization compared to other European countries. Most farms are regulated on basis of nutrients (N, P, BOD) in the effluents. The Danish legalization demands the use of BAT, which in turns inspire the fish-farmers to invest in new technologies. Food safety standards follow EU directives and regulations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increase traceability of seafood supply chain in relation to the more sustainable aquaculture: carbon footprint, other environmental parameters. Adoption of aquaculture to more share the information about the environment

Table 12. SWOT analysis for OXY CLL in Denmark

Strengths	Weaknessess
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Partners in several countries. High aquaculture technology. knowledge of the industry needs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No national funds for the LL . Low per capita fish consumption without a fishing power.
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Danish Lab's technology facilitates the transparency and traceability of the aquaculture sector's information to society. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The aquaculture sector in Denmark has few opportunities to grow due to strict environmental regulations.

- There is an environmental regulation that may be incompatible with our activity.

5.3.4 Bugenvila (Croatia): Business to business

Background: Bugenvila is the restaurant in Cavtat, Croatia focusing on quality control in business-to-business fish and seafood supply chain. Bugenvila represents the gastronomy sector related to the history and cultural heritage of the Mediterranean diet. Indirect communication with consumers will promote seafood meals. By dramatically shortening the supply chain between actual sea product producers and the consumers, Bugenvila acts as an excellent communication channel between the producers and the consumers.

Bugenvila in FishEUTrust: The CLL has been created to increase end-consumer confidence in fish products and thus be able to help increase the consumption of fishery products. The following actions will be performed:

- The mapping of consumer expectations and identifying key characteristics of consumer groups in the Mediterranean part of Croatia (target groups: young families, Senior citizens and their communities).
- To analyze major market players in fish and shell-fish farming in Croatia.
- To present new technologies, products and services to farmed fish and shellfish end-users. As technology evolves, the CLL will adapt and incorporate new tools and methods to facilitate its mission of co-creating and testing innovative solutions with real-world users. The testing will mainly relate to the smart tools to define fish safety and freshness. Feedback will be evaluated (target groups: gastronomy, retailers, individuals).
- To organize an awareness campaign in Croatia (education in seafood cuisine to enhance cooking skills).

Relevant Stakeholders: The main stakeholders involved in the Croatian living lab are universities, companies and government bodies.

	People, consumers	The public (tourists, restaurant guests)
	Government Policy makers	Ministry of Agriculture - Fishery Department, Aquaculture
	Industry, SMEs	CROFISH vl. Denis Varović, Dnevni Ulov d.o.o., Kornat Ittica d.o.o., Đido - uzgoj ribe i školjaka, Apnea d.o.o., Orka d.o.o., Cromaris
	Academia University	Rudjer Bošković Institute, University of Dubrovnik

Contextual analysis: PESTLE & SWOT: PESTLE and SWOT analysis for Bugenvila CLL are presented in Tables 13 and 14, respectively.

Table 13 PESTLE analysis Bugenvila CLL

Political	Economic	Sociocultural
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CLL projects must align with regulations. • Support industry in policy discussions and try to influence to get aquaculture license. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CLL has not received any external funding. • No evidence of funding available from national or European funding programs to support LL activities. • Cost workers are the same than the rest economical sector. • There is a disparity exists in the VAT rates, with frozen seafood incurring a 25% VAT, while fresh seafood is subject to a 5% VAT. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Medium-low EU rate fish consumption per capita. • Consumer perceptions play a crucial role in shaping the direction of research and innovation projects. • NGOs are focus on aquaculture messages around sustainability, environmental conservation, responsible practices, and community engagement.

	This variance serves as an incentive for local production.	
Technological	Legal	Environmental
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Living labs adapt and incorporate new tools and methods to facilitate their mission of co-creating and testing innovative solutions RAS. Biotechnology, RAS, Automatization, Bigdata, Analysis, AI 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Croatia, as a member of the EU, aligns its food safety standards with EU directives and regulations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Environmental regulations in Croatia play a significant role in shaping the operations of new aquaculture farms. Environmental regulations are aimed at ensuring that aquaculture activities are conducted in a manner that minimizes harm to the environment and maintains the sustainability of aquatic ecosystems. International cooperation and research on climate change impacts on marine ecosystems are also important for addressing these issues for Croatian CLL.

Table 14. SWOT analysis for Bugenvila CLL

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The ability to function both as a consumer and a provider within the fish supply chain simultaneously. The liberty to innovate and develop novel products. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No relationship with retailers and individual end-users.
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Access to a large number of consumers. Prospects for fresh business models and product offerings. Enhancing consumer demand for fish through improved product promotion. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adverse cash flow effects resulting from development of new technologies within the core business. Increased operational costs.

5.3.5 IPMA (Portugal): Consumer

Background: IPMA's aquaculture research station is known in Portugal by EPPO (Estação Piloto de Piscicultura de Olhão). It is a core facility dedicated to marine biology and aquaculture research. This facility has conditions for training students and provides support for technology transfer to fish farmers. EPPO holds breeders of several fish species (eg. *A. regius*, *S. aurata*, *Epinephelus marginatus*, *S. senegalensis*, *Dicentrarchus labrax*, *Diplodus* spp.), having the knowledge to breed these species and rear them from egg until adult stage. The main areas of research developed at EPPO are new species for aquaculture: development of rearing protocols, feeding and Nutrition, Bio-indicators of fish health and welfare, Sustainable and environmentally friendly production systems, carried out with the support of multidisciplinary and integrated analytical capacity.

Infrastructure: The facilities available for the CLL contain rearing systems (different volume tanks) located indoors and outdoors, different rearing systems (flow-through, RAS, IMTA), and laboratories to assess fish nutritional and physiological conditions or pollutants in the water. There are key technologies that will be at the core of CLL operation, namely, state-of-the-art cultivation of fish, including the integrative technologies that ensure the pilot-scale operation of IMTA (Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture) and RAS (Recirculated Aquaculture Systems) as well as technologies ensuring a responsive, accurate, and smart water monitoring system for oxygen, nutrients, and other abiotic parameters must be in place with its set of specific sensors. In addition, functional aquafeeds of high nutritional value, using alternative ingredients to fish meals and oils and supplements, and the optimization and development of analytical tools to promote fish condition with a holistic approach are necessary. Moreover, in post-production, a whole array of

analytical technologies is concerned with analyzing the nutritional value and ascertaining the authenticity and absence of contaminants in the farmed seafood product. IT technologies shall be incorporated into the operation of CLL in the following years, representing an ideal environment for FishEUTrust technologies.

IPMA in FishEUTrust: IPMA is the partner running the CLL, which will be concerned with the issues of quality and trust that have been plaguing the relationship between aquaculture products and consumers, especially in conservative Southern European markets with a long tradition of high per capita seafood consumption, as is the case of Portugal. Consumer myths include the existence of contaminants, such as antibiotic, anti-parasitic, and other pharmaceutical residues in farmed seafood, which pose a risk to human health and that farmed fish have a much lower nutritional value than wild seafood. Questions related to the nutritional value of the ingredients used in aquafeeds contribute to consumer mistrust. Welfare issues will also be addressed.

The IPMA CLL covers four main areas:

- Provision of aquaculture and wild fish (sea bream) and mussels (WP4)
- Awareness-raising of society on marine aquaculture procedures, highlighting the excellent nutritional quality of seafood products and promoting healthy feeding habits in children
- Training and development of capacities in the sector's stakeholders, thereby updating methodologies and demonstrating tools for more sustainable aquaculture with improved welfare and better nutritional quality
- Opening cooperative paths and venues for testing the developed FishEUTrust technologies (smart tools for food safety and quality), exchange of information and building of partnerships and collaborations.

It is also planned that IPMA will organize citizen awareness on marine aquaculture production, where several aspects of marine aquaculture rearing and research will be discussed with visitors. For example, the fair in Tavira in 2018 and 2019 reached around 60.000 citizens.

Relevant Stakeholders: IPMA is embodied with the mission to support government, administration and producers in areas related with ocean and atmosphere. Over the years, IPMA was built a network with different stakeholders.

	People, consumers	Schools (undergraduate and graduate students), Município de São Brás de Alportel
	Government Policy makers	ARDITI (Agência Regional para o Desenvolvimento da Investigação, Tecnologia e Inovação), ASAE (Autoridade de Segurança Alimentar e Económica, The Economic and Food Safety Authority), DGAV (Direção-Geral de Alimentação e Veterinária), DGPM (Direção-Geral de Política do Mar do Ministério da Economia e Mar, Directorate-General for Maritime Policy)
	Industry, SMEs	APA (Associação Portuguesa de Aquaculturas), Atlantik Fish, Bivalvia, Continente, Cooperativa de Viveiristas da Ria Formosa, DocaPesca, Flatlantic, Jerónimo Martins, NaturaFish, Necton, Oceano Fresco, Piscicultura do Vale da Lama, RiaSearch, SeaEntia, Sparos e Viveiros da Espargueira
	Academia University	CIIMAR, FFUP (Faculdade de Farmácia da Universidade do Porto), UTAD (Universidade de Trás-os-Montes e Alto Douro)

Contextual analysis: PESTLE & SWOT: PESTLE and SWOT analysis for IPMA CLL are presented in Tables 15 and 16, respectively.

Table 15. PESTLE analysis for IPMA CLL in Portugal

Political	Economic	Sociocultural
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Under Government rules • Advice to the Portuguese government. • Distribute data and reports to companies and society. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National and European funding programs support LL activities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Highest EU rate fish consumption per capita. • Contribute with information related analyzed samples.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support on the policies applied to aquaculture action. 		
Technological	Legal	Environmental
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aquaculture facilities for fish growth. RAS. Aquaculture sampling and analysis. Database available for quintuple helix. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The governance structure of IPMA's CLL is expected to be collaborative. Stakeholders are going to participate. Food safety standards follow EU directives and regulations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There are Environmental regulations inform the licensing and regular operation of aquaculture farms. The set-up a strategy to communicate and explained to consumer the sustainable development of aquaculture.

Table 16. SWOT analysis for IPMA CLL in Portugal

Strength	Weakness
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Deep understanding of aquaculture and seafood science and technology. Ample technological means for analysis of nutritional value, contaminant presence, and authenticity certification. Marine core facility holding different aquatic marine species and the control of the life cycle for most of the species. Rearing systems of different volumes, indoors and outdoors, adequate to the rearing of the different stages of development (breeders, eggs, larvae, juveniles, on growing). Laboratories fully equipped for general biochemical and enzymatic determinations, fish pathology and molecular biology. Human resources with vast expertise. Competence on organizing technical meetings with different stakeholders. Actions aquaculture activities to consumers. Previous experience in multiple dissemination actions (ex: student visits to our facility, technical contents, films, participation in fairs). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The absence of a demanding societal environment that stimulates connectivity and networking in a quintuple helix logic. Low participation/contribution from stakeholders to the working plan. Communication problems. Current frequent human financial constraints that limit the timely execution of projected activities.
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The aquaculture sector is pressured to increase production and evolve to satisfy new consumers and fill emerging market gaps. Importance of blue biotechnology. Importance of aspects related with food safety and traceability. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Funding difficulties that may hamper the continuation of an active IPMA CLL dedicated to the relationship between aquaculture and consumer.

A joint analysis of the results obtained in the PESTLE and SWOT analyses of FishEUTrust CLLs points out to elements common to all of them, among which the following stand out:

- The CLLs can act as a communication interface in all agents of the quintuple helix
- The CLLs do not have any national or European funding for their financing and sustainability
- The CLLs have access to very important technologies to improve consumer confidence in the products of the fishery culture
- Environmental regulations often become a wall that makes it impossible for aquaculture activity to continue to develop within the European Union.

The PESTLE analysis of the five CLLs shows significant differences between them. The largest is IPMA, a Portuguese public body and a research centre with very high human, political and technological capabilities but with less intense interaction with the private sector and consumers. The Croatian CLL at Bugenvila has been recently created and has a good connection with consumers. However, it requires a significant investment to increase methodological and technological training. The CLL led by Oxyguard is powerful in the technological area and its relationship with the industry sector; however, it must improve the connection with other agents of the quintuple helix, such as consumers or political and social agents.

ABT in Malata and CETGA in Spain are the most similar to the planned functions for the CLLs. They have a strong presence in the private sector, with universities and a technological and methodological base that allows them to undertake any demonstration project. However, they have shortcomings in accessibility and communication with consumers.

What is relevant about this analysis is that the sum of the capabilities of the five CLLs analyzed completes all the capabilities that an LL must possess. Through this exercise, an exchange of experiences and knowledge can occur between them to co-create an LL for the European aquaculture sector.

6 Living Labs and projects with synergies with FEUT LLs

Task 1.3 aimed at consolidating the synergies with an existing network of LLs to implement an inclusive EU-level Web of LLs. It builds on the stakeholder mapping performed in T1.1 and proposes a European-level web of LLs and identify cross-pollination potential to inform T1.5. It also offers input for the furthering of CLLs implementation.

6.1 Methodology

Task 1.1 and Task 1.3 worked together to define the criteria for the LLs to be considered for creating synergies with FishEUTrust CLLs. In this process, the task leaders identified the lack of common definition for LLs in aquaculture and decided that all mechanisms which support innovation by means of co-creation with the industry and citizens should be considered. Therefore, desk research was implemented in T1.3 to identify 1) projects that have implemented LLs which are operational, 2) research infrastructures and other facilities dedicated to R&D and innovation in aquaculture, 3) recent projects that are establishing LLs in the field of aquaculture and correlated areas.

For 1), the search indicated various projects and initiatives funded by H2020, the Sustainable Aquaculture in the Western Mediterranean Blue Economy Initiative (WestMed) and Interreg's Baltic Blue Growth Initiative or Initiatives that were no longer traceable, for example: North Atlantic Whitefish Marine Living Lab (WhiteFishMaLL) (Viðarsson et al, 2015). The so-called project-based LLs consisted technically of LLs, pilot tests or demonstration sites.

For 2) the search comprised the aquaculture dedicated infrastructures named among the DEIMS-SDR (Dynamic Ecological Information Management System - Site and dataset registry) and the research facilities participating in the transnational call of the project AQUAculture infrastructures for Excellence in European Fish Research 3.0 (AQUAEXCEL3.0). The search for research infrastructures in place of LLs felt justified by the promotion of open innovation model, which include research infrastructures at the supply side of new knowledge and as effective testbeds of innovative devices that can be benchmarked against mature technologies in performing research (ESFRI, 2018). All the research infrastructures and research facilities identified were listed as fiches in a catalogue annexed to this report (Annex 2).

For 3) the list of projects of the HE's EU Mission 'Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2023' – Call for Proposal 2022¹¹, allowed to gather a list of 38 projects, which was screened for aquaculture, living labs, pilot sites, and demonstration sites that the researchers could identify potential interests for FishEUTrust CLLs. Of this list's 27 projects, 12 were identified as of interest for building synergy with FishEUTrust CLLs. Those were added by two projects were funded by the ERA-NET Cofund on the Blue Bioeconomy and a H2020 project. The list of projects is available in Annex 3.

Two LLs devoted to aquaculture were identified: the Ilvo Marine Living Lab, an independent government research institute from Flanders, and the S2AQUAcoLAB based in Portugal. These two were listed as benchmarks with text boxes as benchmarks.

6.2 Living Labs and research infrastructure for building synergies with FishEUTrust CLLs

The search for Aquaculture LLs for the creation of the EU-wide web of living labs for synergies with FishEUTrust LLs only yielded two operational LLs with this specific focus (ILVO's Marine Living Lab and Collaborative Laboratory in Sustainable and Smart Aquaculture - S2AQUAcoLAB). The Blue

¹¹ https://oceans-and-fisheries.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-06/2023-06-29-List-of-projects-eu-mission-call_en.pdf

Living Lab (<https://www.nausicaa.fr/en/committed-center/blue-living-lab>), although called by LL, including in its name, operates as an incubator. Other LLs were not operational, or it was impossible to trace their activities beyond the life cycle of the projects that originated them.

6.2.1 Benchmark living labs in aquaculture

Two LLs were identified with a clear mission to serve in the aquaculture field and were defined as the ILVO's Marine Living Lab and the Collaborative Laboratory Sustainable and Smart Aquaculture (S2AQUAcoLAB). They are placed in boxes 1 and 2 for their potential role as benchmarks for implementing the methodology specific to LLs.

Box 1. Benchmark 1: ILVO Marine Living Lab

ILVO Marine Living Lab
<p>Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (ILVO) is an independent scientific research institute of Flanders' Government. ILVO's task is to generate knowledge for more sustainability in the agriculture, fisheries and agri-food sectors. Starting from a strong anchor in Flanders, their work extends throughout Belgium, Europe and the rest of the world.</p> <p>ILVO's Marine Living Lab strives for accelerated and sustainable innovation in the blue sectors. The living lab has expertise and a broad network in fisheries, the marine environment, marine production, marine biotechnology and the blue economy in general. It stimulates collaboration with and between (potential) partners through substantiated communication and broad publicity. It offers to the marine entrepreneur an integrated package of services and infrastructure, with a focus on innovation and sustainability. The keyword is co-creation, in both directions. In other words, the Marine Living Lab offers expertise, but is also requesting new expertise and technology that can bring about accelerated and sustainable innovation in the blue sectors.</p> <p>ILVO's Marine Living Lab stands for sustainable blue innovation for and together with all actors active on and around the sea, especially fisheries and aquaculture, including processing, retail and food quality, and (bio) technology companies interested in the exploitation of well-known and less known aquatic molecules (blue biotech), sand extraction, dredging, wind energy, and other actors linked to impact reduction, marine spatial planning, coastal protection and nature conservation.</p> <p><i>Expertise and infrastructure</i></p> <p>ILVO counts with 600 employees, advanced research infrastructure and extensive network of stakeholders. ILVO's specialized labs, aquaculture facilities, experimental rooms and equipment, and access to research vessels, are available for the Marine Living Lab.</p> <p style="text-align: right;">https://ilvo.vlaanderen.be/en/living-labs/marine-living-lab</p>

These LLs are of interest as a benchmark because of how they are publicly announced, their services, and their expressed focus on co-creating innovations with the industry. The information on how the formalization of the constructs of LLs, as provided by Westerlund et al. (2018), is a valuable learning resource and provides instruction material for the CLLs being implemented.

Box 2: Benchmark 2: S2AQUAcoLAB

Collaborative Laboratory in Sustainable and Smart Aquaculture - S2AQUAcoLAB
<p>The S2AQUAcoLAB is a private non-profit institution, founded in 2021, whose mission is to elevate aquaculture to a new level by playing an interface role between academia, research and industry. S2AQUAcoLAB performs research in production optimization, identification of health and welfare markers, climate change adaptations and development of new products for market diversification. Its members include 15 companies and entities, in addition to 49 associated researchers, with proven experience and numerous scientific publications in the area.</p>

S2AQUACoLAB provides **dedicated services in the aquaculture area**, being a **strategic partner** in the study, planning and determination of layouts that help the production industry to grow. It is committed to improving production, optimization of cultivation and nutrition protocols, and development of new, more sustainable formulas.

S2AQUACoLAB is committed to boosting aquaculture, **fostering the creation of analytical tools and the implementation of new technologies that facilitate production management**.

The services offered by the S2AQUACoLAB consist of:

- Technical, tailor made and specialized training in aquaculture
- Cultivation and pilot production of algae, fish, bivalves and other marine organisms
- "In vivo" trials with marine organisms (algae, fish, bivalves and other invertebrates) and model organisms
- "In vitro" assays
- Laboratory analysis
- Gene expression
- Pathology
- Chemistry (e.g. nutrients)
- Biochemistry (e.g. enzymatic activity, proximate composition)
- Microbiome
- Animal welfare
- Research and innovation in production
- Technical consultancy (reproduction management, new species, zootechnics, management and selection of areas for aquaculture)
- Data acquisition, technology and modelling
- Fish growth modelling
- Prediction of meteoceanographic conditions
- Definition, conception and elaboration of aquaculture projects onshore, inshore and offshore
- Project support
- Activities and events (organization of scientific events)
- Development and management of research projects
- Support to the sector (e.g. aquaculture implementation support)

<https://www.s2aquacolab.pt/>

6.2.2 Research infrastructures collaborating for innovation in aquaculture

Table 17 shows the research infrastructures identified as supporting research and innovation with stakeholders of the aquaculture sector. In the numbered column, infrastructures from 1 to 22 are research centers and or facilities which perform novel research, experimentation and support to innovation on demand by clients, which can be from government, for policy advise mostly, companies, associations or other stakeholder types.

Infrastructures from 23 to 27 are the ones performing support to aquaculture research and/or ecosystems restoration support. They are catalogued among the DEIMS-SDR (Dynamic Ecological Information Management System - Site and dataset registry), which is an information management system powered by eLTER, the Integrated European Long-Term Ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological Research. They are facilities with an LTER site (Long-term Ecosystem research site) and a physical structure that is an ecological station. Infrastructure 22, South Bohemian Research Center of Aquaculture and Biodiversity of Hydrogenases (CENAKVA), belongs to both lists of LTER-Sites and research infrastructure located at a university centre, the Faculty of Fisheries and Protection of Waters of the University of South Bohemia in Ceské Budejovic, Czech Republic.

Table 17. European research infrastructures supporting innovation in aquaculture

N.	Research Infrastructures Operating in Aquaculture
1	<p>National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment (INRAE), Multi-location, France Facilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experimental Fish Culture Station of Monts D'Arrée, Sizun (https://eng-peima.rennes.hub.inrae.fr/) • Fish nutrition Farms and Platform, St Pée sur Nivelles, Donzacq, Lees Athas (https://eng-aquapole.bordeaux-aquitaine.hub.inrae.fr/presentation/locations/saint-pee-sur-nivelles) • Fish Infectiology Platform, Jouy-en-Josas, (https://www6.jouy.inrae.fr/ierp_eng/) <p>Fish Physiology and Genomics Facility, Rennes (https://eng-lpgp.rennes.hub.inrae.fr/)</p>
2	<p>Institute of Marine Research, Norway https://www.hi.no/en/hi/radgivning/aquaculture</p>
3	<p>Aquaculture Institute Torre de la Sal (IATS), Castellón, Spain (https://iats.csic.es/?lang=en) Experimental tanks, https://iats.csic.es/fish-culture/?lang=en</p>
4	<p>Hellenic Center for Marine Research (HCMR) https://imbcc.hcmr.gr/ and https://imbcc.hcmr.gr/infrastructures/facilitiesimbcc/</p>
5	<p>Research Institute for Fisheries and Aquaculture (HAKI), Szarva, Hungary https://haki.naik.hu/en/organizations/research-institute-for-fisheries-and-aquaculture</p> <p>Facilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RECIRK (https://aquaexcel.eu/haki-recirk/) <p>Outdoor experimental pond system (https://aquaexcel.eu/haki-oeps/)</p>
6	<p>French Research Institute for Exploitation of the Sea (IFREMER), Multi-location, France Facilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Palavas Experimental Aquaculture Research Station, Palavas https://www.was.org/aqua18pressconference/_documents/IFremer_PressRelease.pdf, • La Tremblade Experimental Aquaculture Research Station, La Tremblade (https://asim.ifremer.fr) <p>Mollusc Experimental Platform of Bouin, Bouin (https://en.ifremer.fr/Research-Technology/Scientific-departments/Department-of-Biological-Resources-and-Environment/Mollusc-Health-Genetics-and-Microbiology-research-unit)</p>
7	<p>NOFIMA Research station for Sustainable Aquaculture, Norway https://nofima.com/facility/research-station-for-sustainable-aquaculture/</p>
8	<p>Centre for Fisheries and Aquaculture (SEALAB) Norway https://www.ntnu.edu/sealab</p>
9	<p>ECOQUA University Institute (IU-ECOQUA), Telde, Spain, https://www.ecoaqua.eu/en/taliarte.html</p> <p>Facilities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Warm Water Species Selection Unit (https://aquaexcel.eu/ulpgc-wwssu/) • Marine Bio-Assays Station (https://www.ecoaqua.eu/en/marine-biosecurity-station-mbs.html) <p>Feed Ingredients and Additives Testing Unit (https://www.ecoaqua.eu/en/feed-integredients-additives-testing-unit-fitu.html)</p>
10	<p>Wageningen Aquaculture, Research & Education (W-ARE), Wageningen University & Research, Wageningen, the Netherlands https://www.wur.nl/en/research-results/research-programmes/cross-wur-programmes/wageningen-aquaculture-research-education-w-are.htm</p> <p>Facilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aquaculture and Fisheries Group (https://www.wur.nl/en/research-results/chair-groups/animal-sciences/cluster-animals-in-future-food-systems-and-society/aquaculture-and-fisheries/about-us.htm) <p>Aquatic Research Facility (https://www.wur.nl/en/research-results/chair-groups/animal-sciences/cluster-animals-in-future-food-systems-and-society/aquaculture-and-fisheries/aquaculture-research-1/research-facilities-carus.htm)</p>
11	<p>Algarve Centre of Marine Sciences (CCMAR-Algarve), University of the Algarve, Multi-location, Portugal https://www.ccmr.ualg.pt/en</p> <p>Facilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ramalhete Marine station <p>Interdisciplinary Centre for Marine and Environmental Research</p>

12	Experimental Platform in Aquaculture (UL-EPA), University of Lorraine, Vandoeuvre les Nancy, France https://www.urafpa.fr/index.php/plateforme/technique/4
13	Nordic SeaFarm https://en.nordicseafarm.com/nordic-seafarm
14	Romanian Center for Modelling Recirculating Aquaculture Systems - "Dunarea de Jos" University of Galati https://eeris.eu/ERIF-2000-000H-0374
15	Collaborative Laboratory in Sustainable and Smart Aquaculture - S2AQUA https://www.s2aquacolab.pt/
16	Ilvo Marine Living Lab https://www.ilvomarienlivinglab.be/en
17	Smart Bay Santa Teresa https://smartbaysteresa.com/
18	National Institute of Aquatic Resources (DTU-Aqua), Technical University of Denmark, Denmark https://www.aqua.dtu.dk/english/research/aquaculture
19	Institute of Aquaculture at University of Stirling https://www.stir.ac.uk/about/faculties/natural-sciences/aquaculture/
20	SINTEF Testbed for Aquaculture Engineering, Norway ACE https://www.sintef.no/en/all-laboratories/ace/
21	Universitat de València Food & Health Lab https://www.uv.es/uvweb/food-health-lab/en/food-health-lab-1285940113499.html
22	Faculty of Fisheries and Protection of Waters, Multi-location, Czech Republic <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • South Bohemian Research Center of Aquaculture and Biodiversity of Hydrocenoses (https://www.frov.jcu.cz/en/faculty/faculty-parts/south-bohemian-research-centre-for-aquaculture-and-biodiversity-of-hydrocenoses-cenakva) • Research Institute of Fish Culture and Hydrobiology, Vodnany (https://www.frov.jcu.cz/en/faculty/faculty-parts/research-institute-of-fish-culture-and-hydrobiology) Institute of Aquaculture and Protection of Waters, Ceske Budejovice (https://www.frov.jcu.cz/en/faculty/faculty-parts/institute-of-aquaculture-and-protection-of-waters)
23	LTSER Mar Piccolo of Taranto, Italy https://deims.org/ac3f674d-2922-47f6-b1d8-2c91daa81ce1
24	LTSER Marine ecosystems of Sardinia, Italy https://deims.org/28407ba7-6efe-45f4-8ecf-efb514e9182b
25	LTSER Mondego Estuary, Portugal https://deims.org/5a38fc08-5257-4b13-8465-1d50ea166b95
26	LTSER Lagoons of Salento, Italy https://deims.org/d7d881a5-69be-4e9a-8717-34d97bdf950f
27	LTSER Ria de Aveiro – Portugal https://deims.org/dfc24538-730e-4e4b-9f04-8e84608b9999

Each one of the research infrastructures is described in detail in a catalogue of fiches presented in Annex 2. They are identified by the type of facilities they are composed of, the services they offer and which kind of support they give in innovation development, their funding mechanisms, and which is FishEUTrust's potential interest in each one of them.

Regarding the interest of FishEUTrust's CLLs in the research infrastructures and LLs mapped, several characteristics emerge from the analysis. They are summarized as follows:

- **Blue Biotech and Aquaculture Monitoring:** Interest in the use of blue biotechnology for sustainable aquaculture and emphasis on monitoring and analysis of aquaculture systems for better management.
- **Recipe Collection and Gastronomy (Gastro Lab):** Collaboration with chefs and restaurants to create a collection of recipes, focus on the gastronomy aspect, presenting healthy fish recipes and nutritional values, and stakeholder engagement through experiments and presentations of fish-related experiments.

Figure 16. Web of research infrastructures and living labs of interest to FishEUTrust CLLs

- **Health and Nutritional Aspects:** Performing an analysis of food components to ensure fish health, nutritional status, and quality of fish raised in recirculating aquaculture systems.
- Research and development infrastructure: Availability of high-tech research equipment, extensive Research, Development and Innovation (RDI) activities.

- **Aquaculture system design and implementation:** Designing aquaculture systems for implementation in the production sector and site-testing for experimenting and validating remote operating intelligent sensors.
- **Environmental monitoring and testing:** Monitoring aquatic ecosystems under human impact and testing solutions in river ecosystems facing water contamination and eutrophication and considering areas with high pressure from human activities, stressing the river ecosystem.
- **Diverse testing environments:** Availability of sites for research activities in freshwater, tropical, and temperate environments and testing aquaculture technologies in exposed environments with a focus on fish health.
- **Collaboration and Support:** Openness to project support and collaboration and coordination between academia, industry, and the public sector, as well as emphasis on collaboration to develop new knowledge in aquaculture research sectors.
- **Research focus:** Addressing challenges in aquaculture and fisheries, such as water scarcity and environmental protection and focus on the entire food chain, from production to commercialization and marketing.
- **Facilities for environmental sustainability:** Facilities for research activities to investigate environmental sustainability, fish welfare, etc, and the development of new solutions for the aquaculture sector based on research outcomes.
- **Large-scale testing facilities:** facilities for testing aquaculture technology on a significant scale, in open sea or other types of laboratories.

To identify synergies among the FishEUTrust CLLs and the research infrastructures and LLs mapped, the CLL coordinators were asked to validate the mapping by informing which organizations and CLLs are likely to collaborate (Figure 16). Only the LTER of Mondego Estuary, the Lagoon of Salento and Ria de Aveiro were not considered of interest to the CLLs.

6.3 Projects implementing LLs with potential for synergies with FishEUTrust CLLs

Annex 3 shows the full list of EU-funded projects that are implementing LLs, pilots or demonstration sites of interest to FishEUTrust. Special focus was put on LLs implementation and the identification of the points of interest to FishEUTrust CLLs. From the project summaries, and applying artificial intelligence support tool (Open AI's Chat GPT) to analyse them, it is possible to identify their focus and plans, as well as to extract the potential for synergies with FISHEUTrust CLLs according to the following structures:

- **Focus on sustainable aquaculture:** The projects, such as C-FAARER, COOL BLUE, OLAMUR, and ULTFARMS, are centered around developing and promoting sustainable and environmentally friendly aquaculture practices.
- **Community-led initiatives:** Both C-FAARER and COOL BLUE emphasize the importance of community-led initiatives in developing business models for regenerative ocean farming and low-impact ocean farming systems.
- **Knowledge sharing and cooperation:** FUSILLI aims to support pan-European cities in addressing food system challenges through cooperation, knowledge sharing, and mutual learning. It emphasizes the importance of building urban food plans for a holistic transition. FUSILLI project is an inspiration to FishEUTrust also for the LL governance structures established within the LLs and the local communities.
- **Marine Protected Areas management:** BLUE4all focuses on effective, efficient, and resilient management of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) across various regions, aiming to create replicable tools and a Blueprint Platform for co-creating effective MPAs.
- **Citizen involvement in marine ecosystem restoration:** OCEAN CITIZEN stands out for its approach to restoration by involving citizens and local stakeholders. The project aims to restore neglected marine biomes and emphasizes ecological, societal, and economic benefits for local communities.

- **Restoration of river basins:** DANUBE4ALL focuses on the restoration of the Danube River basin through a co-creation process with stakeholders. It aims to improve ecological status, biodiversity, and ecosystem connectivity in the Danube region.
- **Multi-Use Low-Trophic Aquaculture (MU-LTA):** OLAMUR and ULTFARMS both aim to demonstrate sustainable commercial solutions for aquaculture, particularly in the North and Baltic Seas. OLAMUR specifically focuses on multi-use low-trophic aquaculture within wind farms.
- **Youth involvement in ocean restoration:** FLOW emphasizes the involvement of young people in restoring oceans and waters, bringing together diverse youth from across Europe to co-create actions with policymakers and researchers.
- **Innovation ecosystem for river governance:** EcoDaLLi focuses on centralizing Danube governance structures and fostering a stronger innovation ecosystem for ecological restoration and preservation.
- **Smart solutions for rural and coastal development:** XGain aims to facilitate sustainable development in rural, coastal, and urban areas by providing stakeholders with access to smart XG, last-mile connectivity, and edge computing solutions.
- **Mediterranean fruit supply chain excellence:** EXCEL4MED aims to establish the Mediterranean fruit supply chain as an excellence hub, focusing on consumer engagement, sustainable processing methods, and valorization of food industrial side-streams. EXCEL4MED is an example to FishEUTrust for its value chain perspective.
- **Fisheries data and traceability:** Fish-X and TraceMyFish both focus on developing digital tools for the fisheries sector, including a Fisheries Dataspace and a fish management system for tracking and tracing safety and quality-critical information.
- **Innovative shrimp production model:** BIORAS_SHRIMP aims to contribute to efficient and sustainable shrimp production by innovating a bio-secure land-based shrimp culture model with a focus on minimizing waste and promoting circular economy principles.

As for LLs, the main reason these projects were selected for synergies with FishEUTrust is their various approaches to LLs, which are applied as platforms for research, experimentation, and innovation involving real-world environments and users (Table 18).

With support of artificial intelligence (Open AI's Chat GPT) to analyse the involvement of LLs activities in the projects, a structure for a basic LL in aquaculture was extracted. It contains the following steps. Firstly, the overall LL framework is to be defined, with scope and objectives by identifying the overarching goals of the LL and specifying its focus areas, considering technical, operational, economic, environmental, and social aspects. Secondly, an analysis of the technical, operational, economic, environmental, and social needs, which leads to the co-design of roadmaps and guidance with stakeholders. These will guide the design of replicable tools for broader application. Thirdly, the practices to be developed by the aquaculture LL are defined, which orients the pilot demonstration sites for the monitoring, simulation and customization of sustainable aquaculture practices, which can include improvements in waste reduction, productivity enhancement, and circular economy practices, based on sustainable processing methods, and valorization of industrial side-streams.

As for the stakeholders, they shall be provided with access to smart solutions for balanced and inclusive development, with facilities to test and analyze the utility and performance of developed digital tools.

Focus shall be devoted on consumer engagement, by bringing together a diverse array of people, policymakers, researchers, and stakeholders. Further, the plan should aim at fostering a stronger innovation ecosystem, by developing a well-connected practices LL system for testing and implementing of innovative solutions. Finally, it is the outline of plans and potential expansions of the LL initiatives.

Table 18. EU-funded projects implementing LLs and innovation co-creation environments of interest to FishEUTrust CLLs

Project	Approach	LL involvement
C-FAARER	Focuses on developing new business models for regenerative aquaculture.	Utilizes sites in Norway and Ireland as LLs to analyze technical, operational, economic, environmental, and social needs. Involves stakeholders in the co-design of roadmaps and guidance.
COOL BLUE	Aims to create a network of community-led initiatives for sustainable ocean farming.	Establishes a Northern European network with a focus on community-led initiatives. Initiates pilot regions in Denmark, Sweden, and Finland, serving as LLs for testing and refining low-impact ocean farming systems.
FUSILLI	Supports pan-European cities in addressing food system challenges.	Collaborates with participant cities, creating a LL environment for cooperation, knowledge sharing, and mutual learning. Aims to build an urban food plan through innovative policies involving stakeholders.
BLUE4all	Aims to achieve effective, efficient, and resilient management of MPAs.	Utilizes 25 information sites and LLs to draw lessons learned from existing MPAs. Aims to create replicable tools through a Blueprint Platform based on the co-creation of effective MPA networks.
OCEAN CITIZEN	Focuses on a novel restoration approach with strong ecological and societal connections.	Involves citizens and local stakeholders in the restoration process across three sites, creating a LL environment for testing and implementing restoration strategies.
DANUBE4ALL	Aims to develop a comprehensive Restoration Action Plan for the Danube River basin.	Implements innovative demonstration activities at three sites in the Upper, Middle Danube, and the Danube Delta, creating LLs for testing nature-based solutions and enhancing river ecosystem connectivity.
OLAMUR	Aims to demonstrate sustainable commercial solutions for multi-use low-trophic aquaculture.	Establishes three pilot demonstration sites within wind farms and the vicinity of a trout farm, creating LLs for monitoring, simulating, and customizing sustainable aquaculture practices.
ULTFARMS	Aims to optimize low-trophic aquaculture production in offshore conditions.	Implements Low-Trophic Aquaculture Pilots (LTAPs) in six offshore locations, creating LLs for testing novel designs and operations unique to offshore conditions.
FLOW	Aims to involve young generations in restoring oceans and waters.	Brings together diverse young people, policymakers, researchers, and other stakeholders in a co-ownership, co-implementation, and co-responsibility framework, creating a LL for policy insights and ocean restoration actions.
EcoDaLLi	Aims to centralize Danube governance structures for ecological restoration.	Fosters a stronger innovation ecosystem with a well-connected Practices Living Lab System, creating a LL for testing and implementing innovative solutions.
XGain	Aims to facilitate sustainable development in rural, coastal, and urban areas.	Implements an aquaculture living lab in Croatia, providing stakeholders access to smart solutions and assessment methods for balanced and inclusive development.
EXCEL4MED	Aims to establish the Mediterranean fruit supply chain as an Excellence Hub.	Implements multi-profile LLs in Malta and Greece, focusing on consumer engagement, sustainable processing methods, and valorization of food industrial side-streams.
Fish-X and TraceMyFish	Aims to develop digital tools for fisheries data and traceability.	Utilizes technology use cases in Croatia, Portugal, Spain, and Germany, creating living labs for testing and analyzing the utility and performance of developed digital tools in real-world scenarios.
BIORAS_SHRIMP	Aims to contribute to efficient and sustainable shrimp production.	Innovates a bio-secure land-based shrimp culture model, creating a LL for testing and implementing improvements in waste reduction, productivity enhancement, and circular economy practices.

This structure provides a systematic breakdown of the LL initiatives, making it easier to manage and implement each aspect of the LL as a project. It ensures that each component is clearly defined and contributes to the overall objectives of the LL. For FishEUTrust CLLs it can be a suitable guide to further implement their operations.

7 Conclusions and recommendations

This report aimed at presenting the results of three tasks of the FishEUTrust project: 1) to map the project's stakeholders, to provide a contextual analysis of each of the CLL sites and project the CLLs in an EU-wide web of LLs. Due to the difficulty to identify enough LLs operating in aquaculture, it was decided to map also research infrastructures of interest to the project and EU-funded projects that are implementing LL which have potential for creating synergies with FishEUTrust. The analysis of those projects yields a basic structure for implementation of aquaculture LLs.

In TO1.1, a total of 471 stakeholders were mapped with the local support of CLLs coordinators. Those stakeholders were grouped both by position in the value chain and the quintuple helix stakeholder framework. All the sectors in the value chain were represented, as well as the quintuple helix actors, although the stakeholders representing the environment consisted of a class more difficult to differentiate exclusively.

During the mapping activities various challenges were identified. The primary challenge, noted across most maps and software types, was displaying relationships between stakeholders when dealing with large amounts of data. A suitable solution to this issue has not been found yet, except for displaying relationships on maps with fewer stakeholders. Another significant challenge was the level of detail provided when inputting stakeholders into the list. Often, the detail was incomplete, especially in the areas of roles within the value chain and categories of the quintuple helix. This led to assumptions during the analysis stage, potentially resulting in the mis-categorization of stakeholders. This mis-categorization could have implications for tasks and work packages relying on mapping activities, signaling gaps or inaccuracies in stakeholder representation.

To address these challenges, a workshop was conducted between partners to standardize the terminology and categorization of stakeholders. The higher level of the value chain was defined, along with ancillary categories, and different roles were allocated to the various high-level categories. After this workshop, stakeholders were re-categorized, and the analysis was conducted accordingly.

Identifying stakeholders falling into the environmental category of the quintuple helix proved challenging. Classifying environmental stakeholders under this model is relatively new, as a quadruple helix model was used in previous Horizon 2020 funded projects. Determining what types of organizations or bodies should be considered as "stakeholders of the environment" is not an easy task. Only 10 stakeholders were identified in this category, and some of them could have been classified under other categories. Additionally, there might be stakeholders placed in different categories that could also fall into the environmental category.

A key lesson learned during the mapping stage was the importance of breaking down stakeholders into smaller groups. Creating a map that included all information required from all tasks, work packages, and Living Labs was deemed implausible. Partners suggested different maps required for their activities, and maps were specifically tailored to fit these requirements. This approach allowed for the use of smaller sets of data at once, making the maps more coherent.

The methodology used from the ISTER project incorporated comprehensive information related to stakeholder engagement in the initial questionnaire and stakeholder list. This approach enabled partners to populate the list with well-considered thoughts regarding potential engagement activities and roles in the project. It also assisted partners in narrowing the scope of stakeholders to those with immediate or specific interests in the project activities, avoiding a broad net across all potential stakeholders with minimal interest, if any at all.

In TO1.2, the CLLs were identified in partner countries covering three different areas, Mediterranean, Atlantic and North Sea, integrating across all sectors of the value chain to support the development, test and validation of the FishEUTrust deliverables: ABT (Malta) – traceability,

CETGA (Spain) – fish health, OXY (Denmark) – data provision, Bugenvila (Croatia) – business to business (B2B) and IPMA (Portugal) – consumer. The contextual analysis was performed for each pilot site, in Croatia, Denmark, Malta, Portugal and Spain, which consisted of PESTLE and SWOT analyses.

TO1.3 identified LLs and research infrastructures of interest to FishEUTrust with the objective to plan a EU-wide web of organizations with which the project can create synergies. 3 LLs, including one operating in the field of gastronomy, and 25 research infrastructures with service offers in the field aquaculture research and innovation. Of the 27, only 3 research infrastructures were not considered favourable for building cooperation for aquaculture research and innovation in the scope of the CLLs activities. Task 1.3 also mapped 12 projects that are implementing LLs in aquaculture and 2 projects implementing LLs in the food sector with potential to build synergies with FishEUTrust. The analysis of those projects allowed for the identification of their focus and plans, to extract potential for synergies with and lessons for FISHEUtrust CLLs according to specific structures that emerged from the analysis. Finally, this analysis yields a basic structure for the design and implementation of aquaculture LL. These are useful to support the CLLs in their local implementation effort.

Recommendations

In relation to the stakeholder mapping task (T1.1), there is the potential to explore other, more technical software to map relationships more effectively, but this will likely only be undertaken if this kind of map is requested by a specific task within the project.

A definition of what constitutes an environmental stakeholder is needed to properly categorize and identify the current and any future stakeholders. As an output of the project, such a definition could be developed by the partners. This could also be a collaborative effort between FishEUTrust and the sister project SEA2SEE, as the definition for this will be needed not only in the current Horizon Europe projects but also in future projects.

Combining the stakeholder list development with the stakeholder engagement task could have been a valuable method to adopt in the FishEUTrust project. However, as the engagement strategy and the stakeholder mapping tasks are separate in the project, and the mapping task began very early, the cohesion between the two tasks was not as strong. Therefore, the opportunity to develop the stakeholder questionnaire with an engagement strategy in mind was missed. **As the stakeholder list offers the opportunity to populate with information regarding potential engagement activities, this could possibly act as a baseline for the stakeholder engagement task to build around as the project develops.**

As immediate tasks following the ones reported here, the recommendations will focus especially on T1.4 and T1.5, although it is recognized the potential of the data and lessons extracted for the various work packages of FishEUTrust, for example, the stakeholders for engagement and the projects for clustering.

Task 1.4: Establish Living Lab (LLs) demonstrator sites of fish/shellfish production in Mediterranean, North Sea, and Atlantic regions. This task comprehends the process for the full implementation of the CLLs and has a wide range of connections with tasks developed in almost all the project's tasks. The research presented in this report, with the mapping of site-specific stakeholders, the contextual analysis performed, and specially the characterizations that emerged from the analysis of both, shall facilitate the implementation together with the input from other work packages. It is noteworthy the constructs and elucidation by approximation with the specific characteristics of aquaculture LLs, which resembles to operational protocols for action. So, **T1.4 must secure adequate communication flow among all the internal, within the project, and the stakeholders, as well learning from the constructs related to LLs and the insights gathered from the characterization of the LL and research infrastructures mapped in T1.3 to guarantee**

the full understanding of the concept of aquaculture LLs and the basic structure to implement the CLLs. Also, leadership of this process needs to be emphasized in view of the challenges witnessed for the mobilization of most of the CLLs.

Task 1.5: Create an open platform for cross-pollination, engagement with other fish production sectors. The mapping of stakeholders and the LLs and research infrastructures, together with the clustering practices to be adopted in WP8, are the basic foundation for the creation of the platform aimed at in Task 1.5. In view of an observed lack of leadership in the tasks leading to the establishment of the CLLs, the cross-pollination may render difficult to implement or lead to discouragement by the local CLL coordinators. Therefore, **leadership must be reconsidered for the guidance of the remaining tasks of WP1. The stakeholders mapped, as well as the LLs and research infrastructures identified with potential for synergy building, and the clustering activities are an important asset to guarantee the success of this task and shall be mobilized following a clear strategy to be built with the leadership support.**

Still for T1.5, the PESTLE analysis showed in this report is useful to identify **common elements of the assessment across CLLs sites and plan to address them in activities of the task.**

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ANNEX 1: Questionnaire for Contextual Analysis of the CLLs

Questionnaire Consultation to the Co-creation Living Labs

This is a consultation with the Co-creation Living Labs (CLLs): 1) about the status of the establishment of the local FishEUTrust CLL, and 2) to identify, by means of a self-evaluation, which external and internal factors affect the operations of the CLLs. The responses to this questionnaire will be used to describe each one of the CLLs within the SWOT and PESTEL analyses framework and in the Deliverable 1.2 “An Inclusive EU LL”, which aims at identifying synergies with European LLs related to aquaculture and other themes at the core of FishEUTrust.

Questions:

1. Do you have a name or a theme for the CLL?
2. Where is the CLL located (Country and city)?
3. Which organization hosts the CLL?
4. What is/are the focus area/s of the CLL?
5. What services will the CLL supply to enforce consumer trust in aquaculture produce in your region/country?
6. Which are the main technologies at the core of the CLL operation now and in the future?
7. Which tools and methods the CLL is skilled to implement co-creation projects?
8. What are the stakeholders engaged/to be engaged with the CLL per quintuple helix group? The stakeholder map of T1.1 (in FishEUTrust sharepoint) is useful to answer this question.

Industry

Industry	Role in the CLL	Level of engagement	Actions to engage with industry organizations

Government

Government organizations	Role in the CLL	Level of engagement	Actions to engage with government organizations

Civil society and associations

Civil society and associations-related organizations	Role in the CLL	Level of engagement	Actions to engage with civil society organizations

Universities and R&D performers

Universities, research and development organizations	Role in the CLL	Level of engagement	Actions to be implemented with universities and R&D

Environmental organizations

Environmental organizations	Role in the CLL	Level of engagement	Actions to engage with environment organizations

8. Explain the governance structure of the CLL, including leadership roles and decision-making processes.
9. What are the challenges to implement the CLL in your country? Please fill in the table accordingly:

Challenge	This is how it affects the CLL	It could be overcome by	With these resources

10. Provide insights into the funding sources and budget allocation for the CLL's operations and initiatives.
11. Explain the strategies and measures in place to ensure the long-term sustainability and relevance of the CLL.
12. Describe how knowledge, best practices, and policy recommendations generated by the CLL will be disseminated to a broader audience and used for advocacy efforts.
13. In building a **SWOT** - Strength and Weakness (internal to the CLLs) and Opportunities and Threats (external to the CLLs) analysis, what are the corresponding elements referring to the operation of your CLL?

Strength	Weakness
Opportunities	Threats

- 13.1 Please indicate the 3 most important elements of each aspect of the SWOT and elaborate on them.
14. Describe the regulations facing your CLL, as for instance those related with restrictions for licenses to aquaculture companies.
15. Are more difficult to get a bank loan to aquaculture/fishing companies?
16. Are Nacional or EU fund available to the CLL?
17. Are the labor cost of aquaculture/fishing workers highest/lower than the average labor cost of the country?
18. What is the average seafood consumption in your region/country? What species are preferred?
19. How is consumers' perception about farmed seafood in your region/country?

- 19.1** How do consumers perceptions affect the operation strategy of your CLL?
- 20.** Is increasing the seafood consumption with the consumer age, yes/no? And farmed seafood?
- 21.** Do people in your region/country perceive seafood as healthy?
- 22.** Please rank these technologies from 1 (most important) to 6 (least important) for the aquaculture companies of your country.
- RAS
 - automatization
 - biotechnology
 - bigdata
 - AI
 - new probes or analysis
- 23.** Are there in your country any law or regulation that affect the competitiveness of the aquaculture companies' vis a vis fisheries'?
- 24.** Have your country specific environmental law affecting aquaculture operations?
- 25.** How do the food safety standards compare against the EU directives for food safety?
- 26.** How environmental regulations in your country affect the operations of new aquaculture farms?
- 27.** What kind of messages about aquaculture do the NGOs promote in your country?
- 28.** How is the adoption of environmental quality seal by aquaculture farms in your country?
- 29.** How does climate change affect the availability of fish and seafood in your country?
- 30.** Does the fiscal regime affect differently wild and farmed fish and seafood? If so, how?

ANNEX 2: Catalogue of Research Infrastructures and Living Labs of Interest to FishEUTrust CLLs

Ilvo Marine Living Lab		Location: Flanders, Belgium Website https://www.ilvomarienlivinglab.be/en Contact info sofie.vandendriessche@ilvo.vlaanderen.be
SUMMARY <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Coordinating Organisation: ILVO, Belgium Participating Organisations: Government of Flanders Year Established: Stakeholder involvement: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Shipowners, fishermen, fishmongers and actors involved in fisheries policy Entrepreneurs and others involved in aquaculture on land and at sea (mariculture). Fish processors and retailers Businesses, government bodies, and other scientific institutions involved in the sustainable exploitation of sand, gravel, wind energy Businesses active in blue biotechnology Government authorities and scientific institutes involved in the protection of natural marine ecosystems 		Objectives <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collaborating with the broad fishing industry and other marine sectors The Marine Living Lab stimulates collaboration with and between (potential) partners through substantiated communication and broad publicity. Co-creation: The Marine Living Lab offers expertise but is also requesting new expertise and technology that can bring about accelerated and sustainable innovation in the blue sectors. Network partnerships base ILVO's Marine Living Lab stands for sustainable blue innovation for and together with all actors active on and around the sea, especially fisheries and aquaculture, including processing, retail and food quality, and (bio) technology companies interested in the exploitation of well-known and less known aquatic molecules (blue biotech), sand extraction, dredging, wind energy, and other actors linked to impact reduction, marine spatial planning, coastal protection and nature conservation.
Value creation type	Co-creation and Partnerships	Finance Financed through the Government of Flanders
Market positioning	Local Government	
Infrastructure	Aquatic molecules (blue biotech), sand extraction, dredging, wind energy	
LL service offerings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cultivation for food, coastal protection, ecosystem management and blue biotech Scientific cultivation assistance and advice Monitoring the impact of aquaculture activities Sustainability scoring Valorization of marine residual flows Spatial planning at sea Lab analyses 	
Interest for FishEuTrust	Good example of the use of blue biotech, aquaculture monitoring and analyses.	

Nordic SeaFarm		Location: The west coast of Sweden Website https://en.nordicseafarm.com/nordic-seafarm Contact info jonatan.gerrbo@nordicseafarm.com
INFO SUMMARY <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Coordinating Organisation: Nordic Seafarm, Sweden Participating Organisations: N/A Focus: aquaculture (seaweed farm) Year Established: Stakeholder involvement: Range of food chain stakeholders 		Objectives Nordic SeaFarm is one of Europe's leading producers of fair-grown seaweed and works with a range of food chain stakeholders to develop new products and services. Nordic Seafarm wants to drive a blue revolution where we can use the ocean to grow decent seaweed as a nutritious crop for a growing population.
Value creation type	Informational, nutritional as well as cooking knowledge for sugar kelp	Network partnerships base Working with Sweden's best restaurants and food companies to develop new flavours and products from Swedish seaweed.
Market positioning	Fish industry and restaurants	
Infrastructure	N/A	Finance No information found about the financial setup of this site.
CLL service offerings	Seaweed production, Seaweed education, Seaweed recipes.	
Strategic interest for FishEuTrust	Collection of recipes, which the LL creates through collaboration with chefs and restaurants	

Universitat de València Food & Health Lab		Location: Valencia, Paterna and Burjassot Website https://www.uv.es/uvweb/food-health-lab/en/food-health-lab-1285940113499.html Contact info foodhealthlab@uv.es
INFO SUMMARY <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Coordinating Organisation: The University of Valencia, Italy Participating Organisations: Department of Immigration and Citizenship of the Valencian Government, VLC/CAMPUS, OPEX Field: Food and Health Research Stakeholder involvement: Experts in the food, nutrition and health sector; the university community; National Government; Public-Private-People Alliance (PPP) for user-driven open innovation. 		Objectives <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promoting innovative development and solutions for health, nutrition, food and physical activity problems from a diverse scientific focus. Promoting health, healthy and sustainable food strategies, models of food educational intervention, nutritional intervention and improvement of the quality of life within the branches of the Universitat, at a local, national and international level. Carrying out health interventions in an interdisciplinary environment to increase the gastronomic and culinary strategies to adapt menus to individuals and/or patients and developing teams, methods and new tools in health environments, nutrition, gastronomy, physical activity and quality of life with applicability to society. Evaluating through clinical, biochemical and genetic trials in order to improve the diagnosis and develop new diagnostic tests that allow the treatment of different diseases. Creating a public-private collaboration scheme for the execution of training initiatives. Network partnerships base Part of the European Network of Living Labs (ENOLL) and Policies for Excellence Office (OPEX) of the University of Valencia. Finance Funded by the institutional innovation programme of the OPEX and by the programme to promote innovative ecosystems of the Ministry of Education, Culture and Sports through the VLC/CAMPUS, Campus of International Excellence programme.
Value creation type	Analysis of food components and pollutants, nutritional analysis, development of healthy and sustainable food strategies as well as on the development of new cooking tools	
Market positioning	Local University Community. National and International Projects.	
CLL service offerings	The specific units of the Food&HealthLL are encompassed in six categories (nutrition, gastronomy, physical therapy, psychology, physical activity and clinical-biochemical-genetic analysis lab activities). They are totally cross-disciplinary and interlinked within the LivingLab. The units, which are set with specific equipment and tool, are the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unit of Education and Assistance for users and patients and focused on nutrition, physical therapy and psychology Unit of Clinic-Biochemistry-Genetics Neurofeedback EEG Unit Anthropometry and Kinanthropometry Unit Gastronomy Unit (GastroLab) Physical Activity Unity 	
Interest for FishEuTrust	Gastronomy aspect (Gastro Lab) is interesting for the project, as healthy fish recipes are presented, as well as the nutritional values of certain fishes and the stakeholder engagement with the experiments. Similarly, the analysis of food components and pollutants in fish helps to secure healthiness of fish.	

Romanian Center for Modelling Recirculating Aquaculture Systems		Location: Galați, România Website https://www.unicer.ugal.ro/index.php/en/about-moras Contact info victor.cristea@ugal.ro
INFO SUMMARY <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Coordinating Organisation: University of Galați (UDJG), Romania Participating Organisations: N/A Focus: Research, Development and Innovation in Aquaculture Year established: Stakeholder involvement: fish farmers, industry 		Objectives The main mission of the Romanian Center for Modelling Recirculating Aquaculture Systems (MoRAS) is to promote the fundamental, efficient and applied research, in the field of recirculating aquaculture systems, by stimulating any sort of collaboration, the exchange of ideas and experience accumulated in this field by the academic community, within the University. MoRAS research centre aims, depending on the provided opportunities, to support the implementation, through technological transfer, of recirculating aquaculture systems and intensive aquaculture technologies, developed within it, at the level of economic and industrial units. The RDI activities are carried out in the fundamental field of Engineering Sciences, correlated to the field of intelligent specialization in Bioeconomy, as follows: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Promoting sustainable, environmentally friendly aquaculture production systems. Developing consumer-oriented aquaculture technologies. Controlling aquatic pathologies through immunological approach. Network partnerships base MoRAS is operational within the Faculty of Food Science and Engineering of the University of Galați. The organisation is contracted for RDI activities for various national and international bodies in both the public and private sector. Finance Various funding streams and conducts at least one current project financed by Horizon Europe.
Value creation type	RDI activities in the field of aquaculture, both nationally and in the European scientific area. Technological transfer.	
Market positioning	Government driven	
Infrastructure	14 laboratories equipped with high-performance equipment for leading exploratory research, including: Extrusion plant Chromatography and microscopy, Cell culture, Histology, Nutrition, Water quality control, Numerical modelling in aquaculture and molecular biology, Bioeconomic modelling in aquaculture, Physiology, Material resistance, Mechanical and tribological tests, Polymeric materials research, Gastronomy. Technology includes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recirculating Aquaculture System pilot plant (RAS) Ultra High-Performance Liquid Chromatography System Laser Scanning Confocal Scanning Microscope Atomic Absorption Spectrometer Continuous Flow Wastewater AutoAnalyzer Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectrometer Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectrometer Tribometer High Performance Computing System Biaxial machine for static and dynamic tests	
CLL service offerings	The MoRAS Center offers a diversified range of consultancy, expertise, training and technology transfer services for the socio-economic environment, in the following areas: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> New production systems Rearing technologies in aquaculture recirculating systems Fish feed or feeding schemes Effects of handling environmental conditions Breeding or rearing technological phase for different aquaculture species Chemical analysis of water by continuous flow analysis Fish nutrition physiology Fish health and technological comfort in aquaculture species Fish pathologies and treatment Kinematics and swimming performance in fish, physiology and metabolism of aquatic organisms. Water quality, biochemical, microbiological and parasitological analysis Drawing up studies/documentation in the field of aquaculture 	
Interest for FishEuTrust	A variety of high-tech research equipment and extensive RDI as well as an aquaculture research catalogue. Nutritional evaluation and quality control of the fish raised in recirculating aquaculture systems. Designing of aquaculture systems for their implementation in the production sector.	

Smart Bay Santa Teresa		Location: Gulf of Poets, Lerici and the vicinity with the port of La Spezia Website https://smartbaysteresa.com/en/ Contact info smartbaysantateresa@gmail.com
INFO SUMMARY <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Coordinating Organisation: N/A Participating Organisations: ENEA, CNR and INGV, Municipality of Lerici, S. Teresa Sea School and Cooperative of Associated Mussel Farmers Year established: Focus: research, technology, sustainable tourism and mussel farming Stakeholder involvement: Platform of cooperation among research institutes working in the area, local authorities (Comune di Lerici) and some SMEs working with natural resources, as well as direct citizens' engagement. 		Objectives Smart Bay Santa Teresa aims to test sustainable strategies for marine coastal resources based on sustainability and blue economy, in agreement with the objectives of 2030 UNESCO Agenda and the Italian national programs for ecological transition, digitalization and economic resilience. This is done by making the Bay an ecosystem model where Nature, man and technologies interact, creating sustainable solutions to fight the climate change. In order to comprehend the ecosystem functioning and related changes through time, it is necessary to conduct high resolution monitoring and long term observations in the environment. This will allow to acquire big amount of data (big data) for describing and understating the on-going changes and building strategies for sustainable management.
Value creation type	Tools for knowing and understanding marine ecosystems. Long term observations obtained via high-tech monitoring systems are the tools for acquiring BIG DATA.	Network partnerships base Smart Bay Santa Teresa is a network of local research institutes, a local school, the Municipality of Lerici, and Cooperative of Associated Mussel Farmers, with the contributes of all users of the Bay. Smart Bay Santa Teresa also collaborates with various bodies, small and medium-sized enterprises, administrations, at a local, national and international level which have as their aim the development of shared projects for the achievement of sustainability objectives in Marine environment Finance Public and Private sector funding
Market positioning	Local government and private sector	
Infrastructure	<i>In situ</i> multi-parametric probes, sensors and discrete measurements (on weekly or monthly base) are used to acquire temperature, oxygen, salinity, pressure, nutrients, pH, pCO and seawater carbonate data.	
CLL service offerings	Smart Bay Santa Teresa collaborates with public and private entities aiming to develop projects on research, technologies, management, training, dissemination whose objective is the development of sustainable actions for marine and terrestrial environment. Services: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Measurement of physiological responses (respiration, photosynthesis, calcification) of ecosystems forming submerged and emerged forests and monitoring the environment where they live. Monitoring of variations of biological and environmental parameters through time and detect the effects of climate change. 	
Interest for FishEuTrust	A site-test for experimenting and validating remote operating intelligent sensors, for non-invasive and non-destructive observation of marine environment.	

South Bohemian Research Center of Aquaculture and Biodiversity of Hydrocenoses (CENAKVA)		Website https://www.frov.jcu.cz/en/faculty/faculty-parts/south-bohemian-research-centre-for-aquaculture-and-biodiversity-of-hydrocenoses-cenakva Contact info Email: sekretar@frov.jcu.cz Tel.: +420 387 774 666
INFO SUMMARY <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Location: Zátěš, Czech Republic • Coordinating Organisation: University of South Bohemia in České Budějovice, Faculty of Fisheries and Protection of Waters • Focus: fisheries and water protection • Year established: 1991 • Stakeholder involvement: Public audience, international research agencies in the world and the EU, Czech agencies, national agencies for water management, Czech Fish Farmers Association, fish farms and other related entities in the Czech Republic around the world. 		Objectives CENAKVA is an open institution that serves as a unique centre of knowledge, science, services and education in the field of fisheries and water protection. It is a large research infrastructure. A unique pond, experimental and scientific background together with close ties to the fishing community in the Czech Republic, Europe and the world, which CENAKVA has, creates a unique unit, which is able to plan and verify future proposals for management of ponds, due to climate changes in the Czech Republic and Europe. CENAKVA is devoted to the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preserving and expanding attained knowledge, and developing scientific, research, development, innovation and other activities • Acquisition of appropriate professional qualification and preparation for research • Life-long learning • Development of international and especially European cooperation by means of the open infrastructure principles. Network partnerships base The Faculty of Fisheries and Protection of is dedicated to aquatic sciences and environmental conservation. It is a centre for research, education, and practical applications related to the sustainable management of aquatic ecosystems and fisheries. The faculty collaborates with local and international partners to address critical water-related issues, ensuring a balance between human needs and environmental preservation. Finance The Faculty of Fisheries and Protection of Waters is a public university, hence benefiting from Czech national funding, which adds up to the economic resources collected in the implementation of its sectoral service provision.
Value creation type	University providing long standing knowledge and technical expertise in the fields of water, fishery, and aquaculture.	
Market positioning	Research-driven	
Infrastructure	It comprehends the laboratories, which are set with appropriate equipment, methodologies and tools, for research, training and innovation, as the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experimental Fish Culture and Facility • Laboratory of Environmental Chemistry and Biochemistry • Laboratory of controlled reproduction and intensive fish culture • Laboratory of experimental complex systems • Laboratory of Reproductive Physiology • Laboratory of Aquatic Toxicology and Ichthyopathology • Laboratory of intensive aquaculture • Laboratory of Molecular, Cellular and Quantitative Genetics • Laboratory of germ cells • Laboratory of signal a image processing • Laboratory of Nutrition Laboratory of freshwater ecosystems 	
CLL service offerings	Analysis of waters, adjustments of fish products characteristics, development of special fish breeding methods, custom contractual research, etc.	
Interest for FishEU Trust	Quality evaluation of fish products and water and development of new knowledge in these research sectors.	

Mar Piccolo of Taranto Long Term Ecological Research		Website https://deims.org/ac3f674d-2922-47f6-b1d8-2c91daa81ce1 http://www.lteritalia.it/ Contact Email: segreteria@irsa.cnr.it info Tel.: +39 06 90672850
INFO SUMMARY <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Location: Taranto, Province of Taranto, Italy • Coordinating Organisation: Institute for Water Research - IRSA • Focus: Research in the fields of algology, biology, ecology, microbiology, oceanography, biochemistry, biodiversity, ecotoxicology and environmental chemistry, with applications in the field of aquaculture, environmental protection and recovery, and biotechnology • Year established: 1914 • Stakeholder involvement: Mainly research institutes, universities, public regional and national entities and economic actors. 		Objectives This semi-enclosed sea is not itself a pilot test site, but it draws much attention from both private and public stakeholders given the plenty of uses that it ensures. As a site linked to IRSA, its main objectives are related to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water management • Water ecosystem structure and functionality • Water treatment • Energy and resource recovery • Remediation and characterisation of contaminated sites Nonetheless, its specific objectives may vary depending on the actors involved and the planned research initiative.
Value creation type	Internal water basin featured by a quite closed system in an urban context, which provides a testbed for water and fishery-related activities.	Network partnerships base The Mar Piccolo is an inner, semi-enclosed sea located to the North of the town of Taranto showing lagoon features. The Mar Piccolo is part of the wider Long Term Ecological Research Network, which also targets problems such as major droughts, hurricanes, the arrival of an alien and new species, or a shift in ocean currents, which can dramatically affect the way an ecosystem looks and functions. Given its width and the co-existence of several actors holding interest in this semi-closed sea, it is an ideal spot to implement research activities via pilot actions.
Market positioning	Research-driven, more specifically, public-led environment subject to private-led and public-private partnership initiatives.	
Infrastructure	N/A	
Service offerings	The services are in the field of fish product production, water management, pollutants management, urban and rural stakeholders' interests. They are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessment of the benthic macro invertebrate community in the Mar Piccolo of Taranto • Biometric measurements and condition index in mussels from the Mar Piccolo of Taranto • Escherichia coli, coliforms and Vibrio abundance from water, sediments and mussels in the Mar Piccolo of Taranto • Study of non-indigenous (alien) species in the Mar Piccolo of Taranto • Study of the composition, structure and abundance of the ichthyofauna in the Mar Piccolo of Taranto • Study of the macrophytobenthos in the Mar Piccolo of Taranto • Study of the physical-chemical features of the Mar Piccolo of Taranto, including metals and organic pollutants in marine sediments • Pagination • Study of the plankton cyst bank in the Mar Piccolo of Taranto 	
Interest for FishEU Trust	Testbed for real-world testing in a populated area subject to a wide range of human activities.	

Lagoons of Salento		Italy Website http://www.lteritalia.it/it/macrositi/it24 http://www.circlemednet.unisalento.it/TWDataPlatform.aspx http://www.servicecentrelifewatch.eu/catalogue-of-resources Contact info Email: Ilaria Rosati ilaria.rosati@cnr.it , Alberto Basset alberto.basset@unisalento.it
INFO SUMMARY <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Location: Province of Lecce • Coordinating Organisation: CNR (National Centre of Research) • Focus: aquatic ecosystem monitoring • Year established: 1990 • Stakeholder involvement: Public audience, environmental NGOs, research organisations, universities, public institutions, European institutions. 		Objectives Monitoring the status of the natural ecosystem. Network partnerships base This site contains the lagoon Acquatina and the Lagoon of Alimini. Furthermore, it is affiliated to theILTER network, more specifically, LTER Europe and LTER Italia. Additionally, these two areas are part of the Natura 2000 sites according to the habitat directive. Finance Financial resources derive from projects implemented in this site, such as in the frame of Natura 2000.
Value creation type	Natural area with ecosystemic value with public interest in its protection.	
Market positioning	Research-driven	
Infrastructure	Laboratory facilities with other services and systems: mobile laboratories; systems for breeding and experimentation on model aquatic organisms, ecotrons, and thermostatic chambers; metagenomic and bioinformatic laboratories; advanced centres for electronic, confocal and classical microscopy and cellular bioimaging; bioenergetic and environmental ecology laboratories and e-Science infrastructure.	
Service offerings	Water and ecosystem monitoring	
Strategic interest for FishEuTrust	Monitoring of pristine aquatic ecosystem in a scenario of human impact due to agricultural activities from the near fields.	

Mondego Estuary Long Term Socio-ecological Research		Portugal Website https://deims.org/5a38fc08-5257-4b13-8465-1d50ea166b95 Contact info Email: anamartagoncalves@gmail.com , jcmimar@ci.uc.pt
INFO SUMMARY		Objectives The objective of the LTSEr Mondego Estuary is monitoring the ecological status of the river estuary to identify responses to nature and human-induced changes. This is paramount in view of the current and future interventions in the region, for instance to enlarge harbour facilities, and to monitor the risk of floods, eutrophication and surging pollution. It is indeed a highly vulnerable area considering the massive industrial activity, including aquaculture farming, and tourism.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Location: Coimbra, Portugal • Coordinating Organisation: Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra • Focus: • Year established: 2011 • Stakeholder involvement: Research entities and universities, industries contributing to the human impact on the river water quality and public institutions. 		
Value creation type	Monitoring and analysis of a river ecosystem in conditions of high levels of exploitation leading to water contamination and eutrophication.	
Market positioning	Research-driven	
Infrastructure	N/A	
CLL service offerings		Network partnerships base The Mondego Estuary is part of theILTER network, more specifically of LTER Europe and LTER Portugal. On a national level, it is a member of the LTER-ESTUARIES - Portugal.
Strategic interest for FishEU Trust		Finance No information found about the financial setup of this site.
		CLL service offerings Services related to this site consist of monitoring of water quality indicators in conditions of environmental stress.
		Strategic interest for FishEU Trust Testing solutions in a river ecosystem in a context of exploitation leading to water contamination and eutrophication.

LTSER Ria de Aveiro		Portugal Website https://www.lterportugal.net/ria-de-aveiro https://deims.org/dfc24538-730e-4e4b-9f04-8e84608b9999 Contact info: Ana Isabel Lillebø lillebo@ua.pt
INFO SUMMARY		Objectives The area of the Risa de Aveiro is subject to anthropogenic pressures that impact the coastal lagoon and the adjacent freshwater areas of the Vouga River. The identification of these impacts is a continuous collaborative work between the research institutions and stakeholders to achieve the main objective of maintaining the natural balance.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Location: Aveiro, Portugal • Coordinating Organisation: CESAM - Centre for Environmental and Marine Studies & University of Aveiro • Year established: 2011 • Focus: Water quality and pollutant monitoring • Stakeholder involvement: research institutes, local fishermen, divers, sports players, owners of tourism companies and institutes for conservation of nature. 		
Value creation type	River area subject to ecosystem-based management in the frame of environmental policies and in presence of anthropogenic environmental stress.	
Market positioning	Research-driven	
Infrastructure	N/A	
CLL service offerings		Network partnerships base This site is part of the ILTER network, more specifically of LTER Europe, LTER Portugal (LTER_EU_PT_009), and it is involved in various projects such as Natura 2000, eLTER catalogue, OSPAR, eLTER (H2020), eLTER PLUS (H2020), and VA Teabag.
Interest for FishEU Trust		Finance The involvement of this site in different projects is a source of financial means to ensure the sustainability of the site and its maintenance.
		CLL service offerings Water quality and pollutant monitoring
		Interest for FishEU Trust Area with high pressure from human activities causing relevant potential stress to the river ecosystem and the several species that live in it.

S2AQUAcoLAB		Location: Olhão, Portugal Website https://www.s2aquacolab.pt/ Contact info geral@s2aquacolab.pt
INFO SUMMARY <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Coordinating Organisation: The Board of S2AQUA which is represented by six of its members and is assisted by the General Assembly and Fiscal Council. Participating Organisations: IPMA-EPPO, UAlg, CIMA, CCMAR, Necton, Sparos, Câmara Municipal de Olhão, Cooperativa Formosa, Docapesca, COOPaqua, NaturaFish, Arditi, IPMA, PL - CETEMARES, Oceano Fresco, Flatlantic, Ria Search, Sofish Focus: aquaculture research and development Year established: 2021 Stakeholder involvement: Local government, academia, research and industry 		Objectives The S2AQUAcoLAB's mission is to build bridges between science, R&D and industry in the aquaculture sector. The Lab is committed to 1) improving production, optimization of cultivation and nutrition protocols, and development of new, more sustainable formulas, and 2) boosting aquaculture, fostering the creation of analytical tools and the implementation of new technologies that facilitate production management. Specific objectives: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improve the aquaculture industry by making it smarter and more sustainable. Optimization of the production of marine organisms. Boost a fast-growing sector as the engine of the national economy.
Value creation type	Putting knowledge and research at the service of industry, to provide innovative solutions and increase the productive capacity of this sector.	Network partnerships base Members include 1 state laboratory, 2 higher education institutions, 1 R&D centre, 1 municipality, 1 producer's association, 1 regional institution whose mission is to promote innovation and development and 9 private companies. In addition, the S2AQUAcoLAB has 49 associated researchers, with proven experience and numerous scientific publications in the area. Finance Various funding streams from both public and private sector, and conducts projects funded by Horizon Europe.
Market positioning	Research and industry	
Infrastructure	Laboratory equipment able to conduct the following analyses: Gene expression; Pathology; Chemistry, Biochemistry and Microbiome.	
CLL service offerings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cultivation and pilot production of algae, fish, bivalves and other marine organisms; "In vivo" trials with marine organisms (algae, fish, bivalves and other invertebrates) and model organisms. Studying the potential of seaweed, which go far beyond food and the application to other sectors, such as cosmetics and pharmaceuticals. Laboratory analysis; Gene expression; Pathology; Chemistry (e.g. nutrients); Biochemistry (e.g. enzymatic activity, proximate composition); Microbiome; Animal welfare. Research and innovation in production; Technical consultancy (reproduction management, new species, zootechnics, management and selection of areas for Aquaculture). Data acquisition, technology and modelling; Fish growth modelling; Prediction of meteoceanographic conditions; Definition, conception and elaboration of Aquaculture projects onshore, inshore and offshore. Project support; Activities and events (organization of scientific events); Development and management of research projects; Support to the sector (e.g. Aquaculture implementation support). Technical, tailor made and specialized Training in Aquaculture. 	
Interest for FishEuTrust	Lab analysis and existing database of aquaculture. S2AQUAcoLAB is also open to project support and collaboration.	

<h2 style="text-align: center;">The Foundation for Industrial and Technical Research (SINTEF) ACE Laboratory</h2> <th data-bbox="948 192 1351 324"> Norway Website https://www.sintef.no/en/all-laboratories/ace/ Contact info Email: Kjetil.ovretveit@sintef.no </th>		Norway Website https://www.sintef.no/en/all-laboratories/ace/ Contact info Email: Kjetil.ovretveit@sintef.no
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Location: Trondheim, Norway • Coordinating Organisation: SINTEF • Focus: Aquaculture technology, marine operations and new biomarine resources • Year established: 1950 • Stakeholder involvement: research, industry and other actors conducting practical experiments. 		<p>Objectives</p> <p>SINTEF is one of Europe's largest research institutes, with multidisciplinary expertise within technology, natural sciences and social sciences. It is an independent foundation that has created innovation through development and research assignments for business and the public sector at home and abroad.</p> <p>SINTEF works especially to test the new aquaculture technologies via practical experiments both under optimally controlled and realistic conditions.</p> <p>Network partnerships base</p> <p>Main sites are located on Hitra/Frøya, Rataren, Tristeinen and Korsneset. SINTEF is well known in the European territory with different sites. Nonetheless, it boasts customers all over the world.</p> <p>Finance</p> <p>SINTEF is an independent foundation with multidisciplinary expertise within technology, natural sciences and social sciences. Being a private organisation, it caters for its economic sustainability in the form of a business-to-business model.</p>
Value creation type	Fully structured infrastructure for technology testing for aquaculture activities	
Market positioning	Research-driven	
Infrastructure	Four main aquaculture sites and a flexible one covering both fjord and exposed site conditions for research activities. All sites may be reached by boat and are connected to the SINTEF network. A commercial fish farming company administers the sites and well-established routines and procedures are carried out for research. The infrastructure is also endowed with a cabinet for data acquisition with various interfaces.	
CLL service offerings	The full-scale laboratory, SINTEF ACE, is open for research and equipment testing to all parties. The research and experimental focus are mainly on technology for operation activities as well as constructions and environment surveillance. This is based on an interdisciplinary expertise in biology-technology interaction.	
Interest for FishEuTrust	Sites with availability for research activities to test aquaculture technologies in an exposed environment.	

<p>DTU Aqua - National Institute of Aquatic Resources is an institute at the Technical University of Denmark</p>		<p>Denmark Website https://www.aqua.dtu.dk/english/about Contact Email: aqua@aqua.dtu.dk</p>	info
<p>INFO SUMMARY</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Location: Lyngby, Denmark • Coordinating Organisation: DTU University • Focus: Technological and biological aspects of fish farming • Year established: 1941 • Stakeholder involvement: research actors, public institutions and industries. 		<p>Objectives</p> <p>DTU Aqua conducts research, provides advice, educates at university level and contributes to innovation in sustainable exploitation and management of aquatic resources. It investigates the biology and population ecology of aquatic organisms, aquatic physical and chemical processes and ecosystem structure and dynamics, taking account of all relevant natural and anthropogenic drivers, being structured in a wide range of related research fields.</p>	
Value creation type	Fully-structured infrastructures for technology testing and research on fishfarming activities.	<p>Network partnerships base</p> <p>DTU Aqua collaborates nationally and internationally, with most research involving external partners. They are part of cross-cutting initiatives like Maritime DTU, Arctic DTU, and Water DTU. Nationally, amongst others, DTU is involved in major projects and centers like the VKR Centre for Ocean Life, the Marine Ecological Modelling Centre, the Danish Centre for Marine Research, the Danish Meteorological Institute, and the Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland. Internationally, they are active projects related to societal challenges like bioeconomy and climate, and blue growth, and in partnerships in, for example, Canada, USA, Australia, Brazil and South Africa.</p> <p>Finance</p> <p>DTU Aqua is economically supported by the DTU and was previously known as DIFRES—Danish Institute for Fisheries Research, which is a state university. This means it receives funding from the Danish government and from eventual projects it participates in.</p>	
Market positioning	Research-driven		
Infrastructure	Fish and plankton research facilities, fish and shellfish diseases facilities, observation technology testing, aquaculture facilities, captive reproduction of eel facilities, shellfish, seaweed and coastal ecology facilities, genetic laboratory. DTU Aqua operates Denmark's largest research vessel Dana and has a range of smaller research vessels. Additionally, the institute has unique facilities for aquaculture research and research into production of shellfish and seaweed.		
CLL service offerings	DTU Aqua has facilities specifically designed and well-suited for research within aquaculture at the North Sea Science Park in Hirtshals, Jutland. These experimental facilities provide the base for the institute's research into aquaculture, farming technology and fish physiology.		
Strategic interest for FishEuTrust	Sites with availability for research activities to test aquaculture technologies in an exposed environment.		

University of Stirling - Institute of Aquaculture		United Kingdom Website https://www.stir.ac.uk/about/faculties/natural-sciences/aquaculture/ Contact aguaculture@stir.ac.uk info
INFO SUMMARY <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Location: Stirling, Scotland, UK • Coordinating Organisation: University of Stirling - Institute of Aquaculture • Focus: Sustainable aquaculture and aquatic food security • Year established: 1971 • Stakeholder involvement: researcher actors and others conducting practical experiments. 		Objectives The Institute of Aquaculture is a research and business hub providing consultancy, scientific collaboration and expertise to develop new technology and practice in aquaculture. It aims at tackling global problems of food security, hunger and sustainability through aquaculture. Amongst its activities are high-quality research, teaching, training, technology development and consultancy.
Value creation type	Fully structured infrastructure for technology testing for aquaculture activities	Network partnerships base It works with governments, regulatory bodies, industry, pharmaceutical suppliers, fish farmers and supply chains to tackle global problems of food security, hunger and sustainability through aquaculture. As a global organisation, it has links and partnerships with over 50 countries.
Market positioning	Research-driven	
Infrastructure	Freshwater sites in Central Scotland, tropical and temperate freshwater recirculation systems in Stirling and marine facilities in the West of Scotland. It is endowed of systems which include recirculating aquaculture systems, challenge unit, constant temperature rooms, hatchery and invertebrate systems.	
CLL service offerings	The marine and freshwater facilities operate to the highest standards and are available to conduct pioneering commercial research at molecular, cellular and whole organism levels. It also offers services for governmental and regional decision-making bodies to advise policy makers, regulatory bodies and business on a range of biological, pathological and environmental issues.	
Interest for FishEU Trust	Sites with availability for research activities to test aquaculture technologies in freshwater, tropical and temperate environments.	

Institute of Marine Research		Norway Website https://www.hi.no/en/hi/radgivning/aquaculture Contact info Email: post@hi.no
INFO SUMMARY <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Location: Bergen, Tromsø, Matre, Austevoll and Flødevigen. • Coordinating Organisation: Ministry of Trade, Industry and Fisheries • Focus: Marine research and monitoring • Year established: • Stakeholder involvement: researcher actors, government, private sector 		Objectives The Institute of Marine Research (IMR) is one of the biggest marine research institutes in Europe, with about 1,100 employees. Our main activities are research, advisory work and monitoring. The IMR's aim is to be a leading supplier of knowledge relating to the sustainable management of the resources in our marine ecosystems, both nationally and internationally, and the whole food chain from the sea to the table. This includes the marine environment, fish nutrition, and safe and nutritious sea food. Network partnerships base IMR is a central advisor to the Ministry of Trade, Industry and Fisheries, the Directorate of Fisheries, the Norwegian Food Safety Authority and other relevant authorities in the development of sustainable aquaculture. In January 2018, the IMR was merged with NIFES – the National Institute of Nutrition and Seafood Research. Finance Government financing and paid advisory work for various actors.
Value creation type	Research stations in different marine environments, with many different fish species studied and monitored.	
Market positioning	Public sector driven	
Infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Chemistry and Undesirables Laboratory performs analysis of undesirable substances in seafood and the environment. We analyse samples of fish, fish feed, other seafood like crab and shellfish, as well as sediments. • Research stations with live fish 	
CLL service offerings	Acts as advisers to the management authorities, the Ministry and other stakeholders. As well as research, IMR also have extensive monitoring programmes that help it to provide the advice. We have specialists in fields ranging from coastal areas and fjords to the wide oceans, and from small plankton through benthic fauna and fish stocks to the largest sea mammals. Other important fields include aquaculture, safe and healthy seafood and climate change.	
Interest for FishEuTrust	Sites with availability for research activities to test aquaculture technologies as well as fish health.	

Aquaculture Institute Torre de la Sal (IATS)		Spain Website https://iats.csic.es/services/?lang=en Contact Phone +34 964 319 500	info
INFO SUMMARY <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Location: Castellón, Spain • Coordinating Organisation: State Agency Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (Higher Council of Scientific Research) • Focus: Aquaculture Research • Year established: 1979 • Stakeholder involvement: researcher actors and government institutions. 		Objectives Two groups: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Live Preys In Aquaculture, Larviculture And Ecotoxicology Group the initial studies of the group focussed almost exclusively on the biology of the branchiopod crustacean Artemia and its use in aquaculture. The utilisation of Artemia nauplii as indispensable live food in marine larviculture, the almost exclusive origin of this resource from the American continent, and the lack of information about the biodiversity and biogeography of the different species of the genus Artemia around the world, have driven the evolution of the group research lines from its creation. • Nutrigenomics and Fish Growth Endocrinology Group The research Group of Nutrigenomics is focus on gilthead sea bream, but also deals with studies in other farmed fish species (European sea bass, common dentex, turbot, Senegalese sole, trout). The ultimate goal is to develop new bio-technological tools for the sustainable development and validation of new fish feeds, using safe alternative raw materials and additives to improve the overall performance and health status of farmed fish, also preserving the nutritive value of marked fish. Network partnerships base In the development of its research work, financed with Autonomous, National and European Projects, the IATS collaborates with several national and international centres, on every continent. Finance Government financing and EU funding.	
Value creation type	Experimental tanks. Houses and maintains fish, molluscs and crustaceans for research purposes.		
Market positioning	Public sector driven		
Infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fish culture • Radio-isotope lab • Cell culture lab • Histology and microscopy • Biochemistry and molecular biology 		
CLL service offerings	Lines of investigation: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dynamics of populations and systems. • Reproduction and genetic improvement. • Nutrition and growth Larviculture and ecotoxicology. • Pathology of cultivated species. • Trangenesis Proteomics and genomics 		
Interest for FishEU Trust	Experimental tanks with a wide variety of fish species to test and monitor fish health.		

<h2 style="text-align: center;">Hellenic Center for Marine Research (HCMR)</h2>		Greece Website https://imbbs.hcmr.gr/infrastructures/facilitiesimbbs/ Contact info Email: msimbbs@hcmr.gr (Aqualabs)
INFO SUMMARY <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Location: Crete and Anavissos, Greece • Coordinating Organisation: Institute of Marine Biology, Biotechnology and Aquaculture (IMBBC) • Focus: Aquaculture research, marine biology and biotechnology • Year established: • Stakeholder involvement: researcher actors, government, industry and academia. 		Objectives Two Research Sectors, the Marine Biology & Biotechnology (MB&B) and Aquaculture (AQUA) Sectors. Focused on aquaculture, genomics and molecular biotechnology, marine biodiversity and ecosystem management. Research directions in aquaculture: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reproduction and physiology • Fish nutrition and feeding • Production technologies • Fish health • Fish behaviour • Biomarkers and bioassays • Fish quality and safety • Aquaculture Genetics • Network partnerships base European and National research infrastructures and also available to third parties from academia and industry. Finance Government and private sector
Value creation type	Aquaculture research and fish health	
Market positioning	Public and private sector driven	
Infrastructure	A wide range of state-of-the-art facilities for Aquaculture, Genomics, Marine Ecology and Biodiversity, which form part of European and National research infrastructures.	
CLL service offerings	In Aquaculture: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Broodstock management • Pilot scale hatchery • Phyto- and zooplankton production • Nutrition and biochemistry • Feed production unit • Fish Behaviour • Fish health • Vaccine development • Toxicology and biomarkers • Sensory lab • Pilot netpen aquaculture farm 	
Interest for FishEuTrust	Fish health evaluations, as well as a look at the coordination between academia, industry and the public sector.	

Research Institute for Fisheries and Aquaculture (HAKI)		Hungary Website https://haki.naik.hu/en/organizations/research-institute-for-fisheries-and-aquaculture Contact Email: info.haki@haki.naik.hu	info
INFO SUMMARY <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Location: Szarva, Hungary • Coordinating Organisation: Hungarian Government • Focus: Aquaculture and fisheries development projects • Year established: 1953 • Stakeholder involvement: researcher actors, government, private sector 		Objectives The institute is implementing a multidisciplinary research work, to provide scientific basis for the development of various fish culture technologies, and for the proper use and protection of the aquatic environment. The three major fields of research are: aquaculture, aquatic ecology; and fish biology. The research work is carried out in the frame of specific projects such as: fish genetics and gene bank maintenance; management and restoration of aquatic ecosystems; structure and function of integrated aquaculture systems; fish feeding and feed technologies; fish biomonitoring and environmental friendly prevention; fisheries management of natural waters; and the development of water saving fish production systems. The scientific work is closely related to the development of sustainable fish production systems, and aquatic ecosystem management. The scientists of the institute are actively involved in various aquaculture and fisheries development programmes in the frame of national and international projects through consultancies, extension services, and training, but the institute also provides laboratory services, and high value fish seed for these projects.	
Value creation type	Internationally acknowledged research and training centre.		
Market positioning	Public sector driven		
Infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RECIRK (https://aquaxcel.eu/haki-recirk/) - HAKI offers two experimental installations, 5 independent recirculation systems, analytical laboratories and a pond system. • Outdoor experimental pond system 		
CLL service offerings	Recirculation systems are suitable for the trials on the breeders, eggs, larvae, and juveniles in almost all freshwater European species. The operation of the experimental system will be integrated with a professional team for sampling and in situ measurements, and with professional analytical laboratories.		
Interest for FishEU Trust	Research programmes are focusing on new challenges that aquaculture and fisheries are faced with recently like: the scarcity of water, the better use of water resources and the protection of the environment; the development of human nutrition; the improvement of food security etc.		

NOFIMA Research station for Sustainable Aquaculture		Norway Website https://nofima.com/facility/research-station-for-sustainable-aquaculture/ Contact info
INFO SUMMARY <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Location: Sunndalsøra, Norway • Coordinating Organisation: The Ministry of Trade, Industry and Fisheries • Focus: Aquaculture, food industry and fisheries • Year established: 1971 • Stakeholder involvement: researcher actors, government. 		Objectives Nofima is a leading food research institute that conducts research and development for the aquaculture industry, the fishing industry and the food industry. The principal activity is research in the following fields: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nutrition, feed and feeding • Breeding and genetics • New species • Quality • Preventative health measures • Production technology and the environment
Value creation type	Land-based research station at with fresh water, seawater and recirculated water, that can carry out biological and technological experiments along the complete aquaculture value chain.	Network partnerships base Have more that 25 year's experience in EU projects and have collaborated with 389 different organisations and companies in 51 different countries. Finance Nofima is run from a business and socially beneficial perspective. The Ministry of Trade, Industry and Fisheries in Norway is the largest owner. Also funded by EU projects.
Market positioning	Public and private sector driven.	
Infrastructure	The station has research facilities for nutrition, formulated feeds, physiology, breeding, recirculation, radiography and metabolism studies. The station also has its own laboratory.	
CLL service offerings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experiments in facilities with and without water recirculation, in fresh water, seawater and brackish water • Testing of feed and raw materials • Research into the determinants of robustness in farmed fish, using swimming tunnels and respiration chambers • Radiography to investigate the development of deformities • Storage and testing of genetic material 	
Interest for FishEuTrust	Research includes the entire food chain, from the start of food production, through harvesting, processing and packaging, to commercialisation and marketing. Member of FishEUTrust External Expert Advisory Board.	

National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment (INRAE)		France Website https://www.inrae.fr/en Contact Phone: +33(0)1 42 75 90 00	info
INFO SUMMARY <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Location: Multi-location. France • Coordinating Organisation: INRAE • Focus: Aquaculture, food and fisheries experimental research • Year established: • Stakeholder involvement: researcher centres, government, private sector, high school students, fishing associations 		Objectives <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PEIMA takes part in national multi-disciplinary research projects that address all components of the freshwater salmonid sector, from the egg to the final product. • Saint Pée sur Nivelle Station: hosts the Nuage Lab (Nutrition, Aquaculture and Genomics) working with the PHASE Department (Animal Physiology – Livestock Systems) and the Ecobiop Lab (Behavioural Ecology and Fish Population Biology) working with the EFPA Department Experimental structures are dedicated to field tests and protocols. • The main missions of the EU IERP are: The production of animals with specific health and genetic status and the realization of experimental protocols in the field of infectiology involving many class 2 and 3 pathogens, some of which are zoonotic agents or GMOs • INRA LPGP's goal is the study of the main physiological functions of fish: growth and reproduction. The research developed at INRAE LPGP are mainly aiming at investigating fish biology in the perspective of supporting a more sustainable aquaculture. 	
Value creation type	Experimental research facilities		
Market positioning	Public Sector Driven		
Infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PEIMA has more than 400 tanks, which allow experimentation on life cycle stages from eggs to large trout. The unit also has a processing unit, for fileting, sampling, measuring and a smokery, in sanitary conditions compatible with organoleptic tests. • Experimental facilities of NuMeA laboratory includes two full-scale experimental fish farms and a dedicated facility with two recirculated aquaculture systems for rainbow trout. • INRAE LPGP includes several experimental facilities: Fish facility, Genomics facility, Histology lab, Transgenesis and Gene Knock-down facility, Bio-informatics 		
Network partnerships base	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • INRAE network • research organisations and institutes (IFREMER, UBO, ANSES) • professional partners (ITAVI, SYSAAF and CIPA) • partners of the European network AQUAEXCEL 		
Finance	Research is developed within a network of European and French partners in the frame of several EU-funded and national programs.		
CLL service offerings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PEIMA Experimental Fish Culture Station of Monts D'Arrée, Sizun (https://eng-peima.rennes.hub.inrae.fr/) • Fish nutrition Farms and Platform, St Pée sur Nivelle, Donzacq, Lees Athas (https://eng-aquapole.bordeaux-aquitaine.hub.inrae.fr/presentation/locations/saint-pee-sur-nivelle) • Fish Infectiology Platform, Jouy-en-Josas, (https://www6.jouy.inrae.fr/ierp_eng/) • Fish Physiology and Genomics Facility, Rennes (https://eng-lpgp.rennes.hub.inrae.fr/) 		
Interest for FishEuTrust	Huge facilities for testing of aquaculture technology.		

French Research Institute for Exploitation of the Sea (IFREMER)		France Website https://en.ifremer.fr/ Contact Email: marie.laure.begout@ifremer.fr , christophe.stavarakis@ifremer.fr info
INFO SUMMARY <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Location: Multilocation, France – 1) Palavas les Flot, 2) La Tremblade, 3) Bouin. • Coordinating Organisation: Ifremer, France • Focus: fish larval physiology, ontogeny and lipid metabolism of the digestive functions in sea bass, turbot and sea bream. • Year established: 1984 • Stakeholder involvement: Research actors and others conducting practical experiments. 		Objectives Ifremer is the largest French institution involved in marine research (1500 people) through research centers and stations in mainland and overseas. It supports the sustainable development of fisheries and aquaculture in the current context of global change and developing the potential of marine biological resources are major societal issues, that IFREMER is mandated to promote. Network partnerships base It works with several organisations, by both providing its own facilities and participating in different projects funded via various financial streams. Finance It receives funding from national and European programmes which add up to the revenue coming from the service provision to its customers.
Value creation type	Fully structured infrastructure for the development of knowledge and practical expertise in the aquaculture sector	
Market positioning	Research-driven	
Infrastructure	1) Palavas les Flot: 3 rooms of which one marine ecotolerance section, including tanks with seawater in flow-through or recirculated water, one from-larvae-to-adult-fish facility, which allows to grow fish from egg to commercial size by offering a comprehensive, also offering a sub-infrastructure for any type of long-term experiment in genetics and genomics and one integrated multi-trophic aquaculture. 2) La Tremblade: 3 sections including one secure platform section, one unsecured platform section, and one experimental onshore concession. Additionally, there is also one secure laboratory section including. 3) Bouin: 3 areas, Experimental Nursery Area, an Experimental Breeding Area for chemical and biological experimental contaminations and a Water treatment Experimental Room.	
CLL service offerings	Experiments setting up breeding from the larval stage to the adult size, experiments on marine shellfish to be carried out and experimentation on seawater fish at different stages of development (larvae, fingerlings, juvenile, grow-out).	
Interest for FishEuTrust	Sites with availability for research activities to test aquaculture technologies, processes, and standards.	

NTNU SEALAB		Norway Website www.ntnu.no/sealab Contact Email: elin.kjorsvik@ntnu.no	info
INFO SUMMARY <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Location: Trondheim, Norway. • Coordinating Organisation: NTNU, Norway • Focus: Salmon farming, aquaculture technology, improved utilisation of “new” bio-marine living resources, environmental pollution, marine exploration. • Year established: 1996 • Stakeholder involvement: Research actors, institutions, private organisations and others conducting practical experiments. 		Objectives NTNU Oceans has as an overarching vision to help solve the big sustainability challenges in the ocean space. Its main goals are to support science, communication, and innovation within key areas of technology, natural science, social science, humanities and art, and facilitate interdisciplinary activity at the borders between these areas. Its research efforts are combined to create new multidisciplinary solutions supporting a sustainable production of marine living resources, energy and minerals.	
Value creation type	Fully structured infrastructure for the development of knowledge and practical expertise in the aquaculture sector	Network partnerships base NTNU Sealab is partner in EMBRC, and our National Center for Plankton Technology (Plankton lab). It is also in contact with public institutions and private organisations.	
Market positioning	Research-driven		
Infrastructure	NTNU Sealab houses laboratories for experiments on cultivation of both marine and freshwater organisms under controlled conditions. Hatchery and recycling aquaculture systems, in addition to several smaller temperature regulated experimental rooms, all with access to freshwater and seawater: CODTECH larviculture laboratory, In-house cultures of live prey organisms, plankton laboratory, recirculation laboratory, analytical laboratories		
CLL service offerings	NTNU Sealab infrastructure provides access to experimental and analytical laboratories. Moreover, it ensures a stimulating and integrated environment for basic and applied research in marine aquaculture, such as e.g. fish functional development and growth, fish nutrition, stress physiology, and environmentally related issues.		
Interest for FishEU Trust	It offers facilities for research activities to test aquaculture technologies, processes, and standards.		

Experimental Platform in Aquaculture (UL-EPA)		France Website www.urafpa.fr Contact Email: p.fontaine@univ-lorraine.fr , Sylvain.Milla@univ-lorraine.fr , Alain.Pasquet@univlorraine.fr info
INFO SUMMARY <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Location: Vandoeuvre les Nancy, France. • Coordinating Organisation: University of Lorraine, France • Focus: freshwater fish culture with facilities adapted to the different fish developmental stages (eggs, larvae, juveniles and breeders) • Year established: 2012 • Stakeholder involvement: Research actors, institutions, private organisations and others conducting practical experiments. 		Objectives The URAFPA-team DAC (domestication in Inland Aquaculture) is a lab from the University of Lorraine. Its mission is to perform research in the field of diversification in aquaculture, with focus on the domestication of new relevant species for the development of European fish production. It carries out experiments on the reproduction function and fish welfare in particular on the environmental control of gametogenesis, broodstock endocrinology, gamete quality, embryo behaviour and comparison of biological traits linked to reproduction.
Value creation type	Fully structured infrastructure for the development of knowledge and practical expertise in the aquaculture sector	Network partnerships base Strong collaboration with external entities who are willing to access their infrastructures Finance It receives funding from national and European programmes which add up to the revenue coming from the service provision to its customers.
Market positioning	Research-driven	
Infrastructure	Two RAS for eggs incubation, two RAS for larval rearing (5 tanks of 700 L each) and 16 individual, autonomous and identical RAS (tanks of 2m3, see picture) for juveniles and breeders, completed by a specific area (6 RAS of 1700 L each) for fish acclimatization step. These facilities are located in isotherm boxes to allow a very precise regulation and management of environmental factors (water temperature, photoperiod, light intensity, dawn and dusk simulation ...).	
CLL service offerings	Service provision to external organisations interested in conducting experiments in a controlled environment.	
Interest for FishEuTrust	It offers facilities for research activities to test aquaculture technologies, processes, and standards.	

ECOAQUA University Institute (IU-ECOAQUA)		Spain Website www.ecoaqua.eu/en/warm-water-species-selection-unit-wwssu.html Contact Email: rafael.gines@ulpg.es info
INFO SUMMARY <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Location: Las Palmas, SPAIN • Coordinating Organisation: Instituto Universitario Acuicultura Sostenible y Ecosistemas Marinos, Spain • Focus: Warm Water Species Selection, marine bioassays analysis, feed Ingredients and additives testing Year established: 1989 • Stakeholder involvement: Research actors, institutions, private organisations and others conducting practical experiments. 		Objectives GIA (Grupo de Investigación en Acuicultura) is a Joint Research Unit of the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC), with a 30 years experience in fish aquaculture RTD, mainly nutrition, pathology, new species and genetics. One of its main achievements has been the clarification of the biological mechanisms involved in the regulation of the functioning of several tissues by means of dietary nutrients, using histological and immune-histological studies.
Value creation type	Fully structured infrastructure for the development of knowledge and practical expertise in the aquaculture sector???	Network partnerships base Strong collaboration with external entities who are willing to access their infrastructures and with organisations involved in projects. Researchers from any EU or Associated State can apply for access to any of the AQUAEXCEL Research Infrastructures.
Market positioning	Research-driven	
Infrastructure	The Technological Scientific Park Building, is used for functions such as, the maintenance of specimens of different species of breeder (amberjack, sea bream, sea bass, etc.), reproduction and collection of eggs of the species, improvement of reproduction using diets with different feeds, photoperiod control, fish fattening and bioassay with bacteria. In the Complementary Module-1, larval culture, preweaning, weaning and auxiliary cultures of rotifers, artemia and phytoplankton are carried out. It is also used for grow-out of juvenile fish, grow-out of tilapia, grow-out of abalone, abalone reproduction, larval experiments and auxiliary diatom culture. Within the SABA it is possible to find chromatography, biochemistry, histology, quality, cell culture, molecular biology and image analysis laboratories, as well as rooms common to the laboratories such as the microscopy, freezing and centrifugation room.	Finance It receives funding from national and European programmes which add up to the revenue coming from the service provision to its customers.
CLL service offerings	This infrastructure provides the possibility to establish a breeding program with its subsequent genetic progress and increased profits, both for commercially well-established species and for new species for aquaculture. Services include genetic advice, construction of genealogies, estimation of genetic parameters and selection of breeders. It also has a self-selection scheme in which users can provide elite breeders or measure the genotype-environment interaction, which is interesting in species such as sea bream produced in very diverse environments. This infrastructure contains control and monitoring of biological, chemical and physical parameters like oxygen, temperature, water flow, feeding or behaviour. Several successful EU and national projects have been conducted of the facility	
Interest for FishEU Trust	It offers facilities for research activities to test aquaculture technologies, processes, and standards.	

Catalogue of Research Infrastructures and Living Labs of Interest to FishEUTrust CLLs

Wageningen Aquaculture, Research & Education (W-ARE)		Netherlands Website https://www.wur.nl/en/research-results/research-programmes/cross-wur-programmes/wageningen-aquaculture-research-education-w-are.htm Contact info Professionals' emails available on the following link: https://www.wur.nl/en/value-creation-cooperation/collaborating-with-wur-1/contact-our-experts-1.htm
INFO SUMMARY <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Location: Wageningen, the Netherlands • Coordinating Organisation: Wageningen University & Research, the Netherlands • Focus: Fish nutrition and health, breeding and aquaculture systems, as well as on shellfish and algae. • Stakeholder involvement: businesses, governments and civic organisations, start-ups 		Objectives Its objective is to improve food and nutrition security worldwide, educate and perform research on the sustainable harvest and production of animal food from marine and freshwater aquatic ecosystems including land-and sea-based aquaculture. Network partnerships base Strong collaboration with external entities who are willing to access their infrastructures and with organisations involved in projects. Collaboration with state institutions are in place as well.
Value creation type	Fully structured infrastructure for the development of knowledge and practical expertise in the aquaculture sector	Finance It receives funding from national and European programmes which add up to the revenue coming from the service provision to its customers.
Market positioning	Research-driven	
Infrastructure	For their experimental work the Aquaculture and Fisheries Group use the Aquatic Research Facility (ARF) of the animal Sciences Group. The ARF is facilitating a broad spectrum of research within the aquatic environment from fresh to marine and from warm to cold water. The ARF has replicated units of pilot orientated, experimental systems where experiments can be done. Research fields are: Fish nutrition, welfare and recirculation systems (water treatment). Unique within our facility are the aquatic respiration cells that gives us the opportunity to perform continuous measurements on the metabolism of fish. The ARF is maintaining a number of carp and zebra fish lines with specific genetic characteristics, these fish are also sold to external parties.	
CLL service offerings	Potential for experiment implementation on the specific areas covered by the organisation's infrastructures.	
Interest for FishEuTrust	Facilities for research activities to test aquaculture technologies, processes, and standards to investigate the dimension of environmental sustainability, fishes welfare, etc.	

Algarve Centre of Marine Sciences (CCMAR-Algarve)		Portugal Website https://www.ccmar.ualg.pt/en Contact Email: ccmarcts@ualg.pt	info
INFO SUMMARY <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Location: Faro (Multilocation), Portugal • Coordinating Organisation: University of the Algarve, Multi-location, Portugal • Focus: marine biology, ecology, oceanography, environmental sciences, biotechnology, fisheries and aquaculture • Stakeholder involvement: businesses, governmental institutions and civic organisations 		Objectives CCMAR-Algarve aims to promote multidisciplinary research and education related with the marine environment, with emphasis on the processes of environmental change that affect marine ecosystems. With a multidisciplinary team of about 250 scientific researchers, well-equipped marine facilities and laboratories and facilitated access to important marine and coastal ecosystems, CCMAR-Algarve develops activities that fall into five different core areas: Research, Training, Business, Society and Collaboration.	
Value creation type	Fully structured infrastructure for the development of knowledge and practical expertise in the aquaculture sector.	Network partnerships base CCMAR-Algarve is an independent non-profit research organization within the University of the Algarve system. It has the Portuguese Institute for Sea and Atmosphere (IPMA) as a strategic partner and, together with the Interdisciplinary Centre for Marine and Environmental Research (CIIMAR), constitutes the Associate Laboratory CIMAR. CCMAR is the lead partner in the Portuguese component of the European Marine Biological Resource Centre (EMBRC). The infrastructure receives approximately 20 international users per year. Approximately 15 projects are run on the station annually and more than 50 projects use the laboratories and platforms.	
Market positioning	Research-driven		
Infrastructure	CCMAR laboratories (Gambelas Campus) are well equipped with state-of-the-art equipment and technology platforms (mass spectrometry, nuclear magnetic resonance, confocal and light-sheet microscopy, electrophysiology, cell culture) for biological research at all levels, from biochemistry to molecular biology, bioinformatics, nutrition, physiology, behaviour and ecology.		
CLL service offerings	CCMAR provides research and technology services supported by its R&D capacity in scientific areas such as aquaculture, biotechnology, biomedicine, fisheries, biodiversity and marine conservation. The CCMAR labs provide access to platforms and support services (Gambelas Campus): Molecular Biology (incl. sequencing and proteomics), Analytical Chemistry (HPLC and GC mass spectrometry and NMR), Imaging (confocal, lightsheet), Cell culture and the genomics/transcriptomics data analysis pipeline (CETA computational infrastructure.).		
Interest for FishEuTrust	Facilities for research activities to test aquaculture technologies, processes, and standards to investigate the dimension of environmental sustainability, and develop new ad hoc solutions for the aquaculture sector.		

ANNEX 3. List of Projects Implementing Living Labs of Interest to FishEUTrust CLLs

Project Title, Acronym, Website	Summary	Duration	Coordinating beneficiary	Countries involved	Connection with FishEUTrust CLLs
Community-driven Farming for the Atlantic and Arctic Sea Basins through Regenerative Aquaculture (C-FAARER) https://www.c-faarer.eu/	<p>The C-FAARER project will focus on developing new business models based on scientific evidence for regenerative, or climate-positive aquaculture. A roadmap and guidance, co-designed with stakeholders, will support ocean farmers in the Atlantic and Arctic Sea basin to develop community-driven business models for regenerative ocean farming. The project has sites in Norway and Ireland, where they analyse technical, operational, economic, environmental, and social needs and create guidance on developing site-specific community-led business plans.</p>	06/2023-05/2025	Trinity Centre for Social Innovation, Trinity Business School (Ireland)	Ireland, Netherlands, Norway	Stakeholder engagement, businessplan, sustainability
Community Ocean Farms and Local Business Clusters (COOL BLUE) https://coolblueproject.eu/	<p>The COOL BLUE project will create a network of community-led initiatives the Baltic and North Sea basins to accelerate the roll-out of commercially self-sustaining, low- impact, inclusive ocean farming systems. The COOL BLUE project will create a Northern European network of community-led initiatives in the Baltic and North Sea basins, initially focusing on three pilot regions in Denmark, Sweden and Finland.</p>	04/2023-03/2026	S.PRO - Sustainable Projects GMBH (Germany)	Spain, Türkiye, Netherlands, Norway, Germany, Denmark, Finland, Ukraine, Greece, Italy, Luxembourg, Croatia, Portugal	Climate-friendliness, business models, community engagement
Fostering the Urban food System Transformation through Innovative Living Labs Implementation (FUSILLI) https://fusilli-project.eu/	<p>The general aim of FUSILLI is to support the participant pan-European cities (and their peri-urban areas) with the aim to address by a strong cooperation for knowledge sharing and mutual learning the challenges of the food system transformation. The main objective is to build an urban food plan to reach an integrated and safe holistic transition towards healthy, sustainable secure, inclusive, equitable and cost-efficient food systems, through feasible and replicable innovative urban policies leading to deploy improving actions in all stages of the food value chain in line with the four FOOD 2030 policy priorities (Nutrition for sustainable and healthy diets; Climate-smart and environmentally sustainable food systems; Circularity and resource efficient food systems; and Innovation and empowerment of communities).</p>	01/2021-12/2024	Fundación CARTIF (Spain)	Spain, Türkiye, Netherlands, Norway, Germany, Denmark, Finland, Ukraine, Greece, Italy, Luxembourg, Croatia, Portugal	Consumer engagement, policy engagement, governance

<p>Blueprint Demonstration for Co-created effective, Efficient and Resilient Networks of MPAs (BLUE4ALL) https://www.blue4all.eu/</p>	<p>BLUE4all aims to achieve effective, efficient and resilient management of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) and networks of MPAs. It will mobilise stakeholders from BLUE4ALL's 25 information sites and Living Labs to draw up lessons learned relative to how challenges were tackled in existing MAPs across the Mediterranean Sea, the Baltic Sea and the North-East Atlantic regions. The objective is to build robust and replicable social, governance, ecological and environmental tools that will be generalised into a Blueprint Platform for the co-creation of effective, efficient and resilient (networks of) MPAs.</p>	<p>01/2023-12/2026</p>	<p>Institut Royal des Sciences Naturelles de Belgique (Belgium)</p>	<p>Italy, Germany, Denmark, Finland, Ireland, Estonia, Croatia, Netherlands, France, Sweden, Switzerland</p>	<p>Governance, technical platform, MPAs</p>
<p>Marine Forest Coastal Restoration: an underwater gardening socio-ecological plan (OCEAN CITIZEN) https://oceancitizen.eu/</p>	<p>OCEAN CITIZEN represents a novel restoration approach based on strong ecological and societal interconnections. It comes from the idea that an advanced restoration programme needs to conjoin ecological perspectives together with societal commitment and clear economic benefits for local communities. Restoration is experienced in 3 sites, representing different marine ecosystems and different environments (subtropical, tropical and cold temperate). The project targets the restoration of the most neglected marine biome, encompassing the various types of marine forest organisms (seagrasses, seaweeds, sponges, corals, gorgonians, etc.). The full involvement of citizens and local stakeholders with a complete business plan is also at the core of the project.</p>	<p>01/2023-12/2026</p>	<p>Universita' del Salento (Italy)</p>	<p>Denmark, France, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Israel, Norway, Spain, United Kingdom</p>	<p>Citizen engagement, restoration, business plan</p>
<p>Restoration of the Danube River Basin Waters for Ecosystems and People from Mountains to Coast (DANUBE4ALL) https://www.danube4allproject.eu</p>	<p>The overall aim of DANUBE4ALL is the development of a comprehensive Restoration Action Plan for the Danube River basin lighthouse developed in an unprecedented co-creation process with stakeholders, integrating citizens' interests to support the Mission "Restore our ocean and waters by 2030". Based on solid scientific knowledge and new findings, the Action Plan will promote the improvement of ecological status, biodiversity and ecosystem connectivity. The project will test and demonstrate nature-based solutions to enhance the free-flowing status of rivers and floodplains, to reduce flood and drought risks and support the continuity of habitats. DANUBE4ALL will implement innovative demonstration activities at three sites in the Upper, Middle Danube and the Danube Delta.</p>	<p>01/2023-12/2027</p>	<p>Universitaet fuer Bodenkultur Wien Austria</p>	<p>Netherlands, Romania, Ukrain, Germany, Serbia, Slovakia, Italy, Croatia, Ireland, Bulgaria, Slovenia, Hungary</p>	<p>Citizen engagement, co-creation process, business plans</p>

<p>Offshore Low-trophic Aquaculture in Multi-Use Scenario Realisation (OLAMUR) https://olamur.eu/</p>	<p>The main objective of OLAMUR is to bring together multi-use low-trophic aquaculture related key sectors, to demonstrate sustainable commercial solutions for both the North and the Baltic Sea. OLAMUR will establish three pilot demonstration sites where seaweed and blue mussels will be grown within windfarms or in the vicinity of a trout farm. The wind farm pilot sites are located in the German exclusive economic zone (EEZ) of the North Sea north of Helgoland, in the Danish EEZ of the Baltic Sea at Kriegers Flak and the third pilot demonstration site will be next to a trout farm in the Estonian Sea near the Port of Veere. All data, information, products and standards for establishing, operating and evaluating will be monitored, simulated, stored and customised as an “OLAMUR digital MU-LTA farm service”. This will provide a solid basis for MU-LTA upscaling.</p>	<p>01/2023-12/2026</p>	<p>HAVFORSKNINGSINSTITUTTET (Norway)</p>	<p>Germany, Denmark, Norway, Estonia, Italy, Lithuania, Belgium</p>	<p>Sustainability, value chain, platform</p>
<p>Circular Low Trophic Offshore Aquaculture in Wind Farms and Restoration of Marine Space (ULTFARMS) https://ultfarms.eu/</p>	<p>ULTFARMS aims to move beyond the current application of Low-Trophic Aquaculture (LTA) systems with novel engineering, technical, ecological and biological processes to optimise production in harsh offshore conditions, low- salinities, and their integration within Offshore Wind Farms (OWFs). Co-development and co-management by research and industry realises novel designs and operations unique to offshore in six Low-Trophic Aquaculture Pilots (LTAPs) in as many OWF locations across the North and Baltic Seas. ULTFARMS will offer services to aquaculture producers for monitoring and minimizing diseases and alien species, managing inputs, optimising sustainable production and demand management including risk analysis.</p>	<p>01/2023-06/2026</p>	<p>Stichting Deltares (Netherlands)</p>	<p>Germany, Belgium, Denmark, Sweden, Portugal, Ireland, Faeroe Islands, Spain</p>	<p>Co-development with industry and farmers, business model, service model</p>
<p>Future Lives with Oceans and Waters (FLOW) https://www.flowhorizon.eu/</p>	<p>FLOW aims to provide insights to support future policy via young generations involvement. The project's innovative design brings together diverse young people from all across Europe with an excellent, interdisciplinary research team, and enables their co-ownership, co-implementation and co-responsibility in actions to restore our ocean and waters. The project will bring together policy-makers, researchers and other relevant stakeholders together, with the youth, and engaging them in cocreation.</p>	<p>01/2023-12/2024</p>	<p>Stichting Radboud Universiteit (Netherlands)</p>	<p>Germany, Norway, Belgium</p>	<p>Stakeholder engagement</p>

<p>Ecosystem-based Governance with Danube Lighthouse Living Lab for Sustainable Innovation Processes (EcoDaLLi) https://ecodalli.eu</p>	<p>The main objective of EcoDaLLi is to centralise Danube governance structures in terms of innovative solutions for improved ecological restoration, protection and preservation of the Danube basin and its Delta by fostering a stronger innovation ecosystem within a well-connected Practices Living Lab System, supported by a digital Portal, completely linked to the Mission Implementation Platform.</p>	<p>01/2023-06/2026</p>	<p>Steinbeis 2I GMBH (Germany)</p>	<p>Germany, Austria, Hungary, Croatia, Serbia, Romania, Bulgaria, France, Georgia, Greece, Croatia, UK</p>	<p>Governance, digital platform, innovation ecosystem</p>
<p>Enhancing Competitiveness, Resilience and Sustainability of Remote Farming, Forestry and Rural Areas through Holistic Assessment of Smart XG, Last-mile and Edge Solutions' Gains (X-GAIN) https://xgain-project.eu/</p>	<p>XGain fosters a sustainable, balanced, and inclusive development of rural, coastal and urban areas, by facilitating access of relevant stakeholders (such as municipalities, policymakers, farmers, foresters and their associations) to a comprehensive inventory of smart XG, last-mile connectivity and edge computing solutions, and of related assessment methods. X-Gain is implementing an aquaculture living lab in Croatia.</p>		<p>ICCS (Greece)</p>	<p>Spain, Türkiye, Netherlands, Norway, Germany, Denmark, Finland, Ukraine, Greece, Italy, Luxembourg, Croatia, Portugal</p>	<p>Digital tools, aquaculture stations monitoring, stakeholder engagement</p>
<p>Excellence Hub in Green Technologies: Introducing innovation ecosystems in the Mediterranean food value chain (EXCEL4MED), https://excel4med.eu/</p>	<p>EXCEL4MED's purpose is to establish the Mediterranean fruit supply chain as an Excellence Hub. It is implementing 4 multi-profile living labs with at least 15 members and 100 participants, focusing on consumer engagement and stakeholders engagement (Malta), sustainable processing methods and valorisation of food industrial side-streams (Greece).</p>	<p>01/2023 - 12/2026</p>	<p>National and Kapodistrian University of Athens</p>	<p>Greece, Malta,</p>	<p>Malta Living labs cooperate relating to stakeholders and consumer engagement.</p>
<p>Providing a European Fisheries Dataspace through a Consultative Approach (Fish-X), https://fish-x.eu</p>	<p>Fish-X aims at developing a Fisheries Dataspace (Fish-X), an Insight Platform, and a Traceability Application to support the objectives of Common Fisheries Policy, EU Green Deal, and Farm to Fork Strategy. The Fish-X Project will produce three technology use cases, throughout which the implementation of the developed digital tools will be tested in order to analyse and report on their respective utility and performance with regard to currently prevailing challenges in SFF. The use cases are in: Croatia (acceptance by small-scale fishers of digital tools), Portugal/Spain (monitoring compliance with new fisheries regulations), Germany (acceptance of the Fish-X traceability application by small-scale fishers).</p>	<p>06/2022 - 05/2025</p>	<p>Transmartech Schleswig-Holstein GMBH</p>	<p>Germany, Croatia, Italy, Portugal, Belgium, France,</p>	<p>Possible collaborations relating to their digital solutions implementation in the application cases.</p>
<p>Traceability and Quality Monitoring throughout the Fish Value Chain (TRACEMYFISH), https://tracemyfish.hi.is/</p>	<p>TraceMyFish aims to advance supply system in three geographically distributed blue bioeconomy value chains, by designing and implementing a iFishManagementSystem that will allow the tracking and tracing of safety and quality-critical information across the links of the targeted value chains:the</p>	<p>11/2021-11/2024</p>	<p>SCiO (Greece)</p>	<p>Norway, Iceland, Denmark</p>	

	Gilthead Seabream/Seabass value chain, the Atlantic whitefish value chain and the the Atlantic salmon value chain. Funded by the ERA-NET BlueBio Cofund initiative				
Aquaculture System for Shrimp and Additional Biomass Circular Production (BIORAS_SHRIMP), https://bioras-shrimp.eu/	BIORAS_SHRIMP wants to contribute to the development of a more efficient and sustainable shrimp production by improving and innovating a bio-secure land-based shrimp culture model to minimize waste, enhance productivity and recover energy and nutrient for additional biomass production, in the view of a circular economy process.		Universita del Salento	Italy, Norway, Malta, India,	